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Performance comparison and flight controller
of circular and figure-of-eight paths
for fixed-wing airborne wind energy systems

Supervisor, University of Trento
Prof. Giulia Giordano

Co-Supervisors, TU Delft
Dr.-Ing. Roland Schmehl
Ir. Dylan Eijkelhof

Student
Nicola Rossi (224876)

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Performance comparison and flight controller of circular and figure-of-eight paths for fixed-wing Airborne Wind Energy System

Rossi Nicola

UNIVERSITY
OF TRENTO

 TU Delft

Abstract

In modern history, the harnessing of wind power as a valuable source for electricity generation has consistently been a subject of interest and study. In the ongoing pursuit of effective and sustainable solutions, airborne wind technology has emerged in recent years. This technology aims to harvest wind energy through the utilization of tethered aerial vehicles and generators, either onboard or on the ground.

The most common systems in this field leverage the aerodynamic capabilities of kites or aircraft to convert the energy of moving air masses into pulling force on a tether. This force leads to the unwinding of the tether itself from a drum, which, connected to a ground-based generator, allows to convert the rotational torque into electricity. The alternation between a traction phase that generates energy and a retraction phase, that otherwise consumes a portion of it, defines what is commonly referred to as the pumping cycle.

In this thesis, a basic flight controller for a fixed-wing airborne wind energy system is developed, capable of simulating the entire pumping cycle of a ground-gen system in a Matlab Simulink simulation environment.

This is done to accomplish the ultimate research goal of assessing the performance of circular flight paths and comparing them to the more extensively studied figure-of-eight paths.

The simulations are conducted within the same working environment, based on the open-source available MegAWES simulation framework where a 150 m^2 fixed-wing reference kite is used. The navigation strategy, based on a variation of the widely used L_1 controller logic, is proposed, tuned and tested in conjunction with a cascaded PID control loop for the attitude control of the kite. A recently implemented adaptation of the winch size and control law is used and tested in the 6-DoFs system, demonstrating its ability to optimally control the tether force and significantly reduce oscillations in the power curve compared to the previous version. A simple state machine is developed to simulate traction, retraction and transition phases, allowing to complete the whole pumping cycle. The developed flight controller, when properly configured, demonstrates its simplicity and capability to successfully track all the studied flight paths, exhibiting good path tracking abilities and robustness across varying wind speeds. Finally, the analysis of flight paths reveals that, for heavy kites, circular trajectories demonstrate comparable, if not superior,

performance in terms of average mechanical power compared to the figure-of-eight pattern. Additionally, thanks to the more compact envelope, these circular paths offer significant advantages when considering the power produced per unit of projected ground surface area. Nevertheless, the figure-of-eight flight path still demonstrates its remarkable effectiveness, particularly when executed in the down loop direction.

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Chapter 1

Introduction

Over the past two decades, particularly in recent years, there has been a notable escalation in energy prices and the consumption of fossil fuels. Moreover, the consequences of climate change have grown increasingly apparent in our daily lives. Consequently, the transition towards an energy system with increasing contributions of renewable energy sources has emerged as one of the foremost challenges of our contemporary era.

The impact and consequences of climate change, now known and shared by scientists since the most recent climate conferences, are also having a considerable influence on today's economy and society.

To face this energy crisis and to keep pace with the increase in demand, renewable energies play a key role to reduce the dependence on fossil fuels and mitigate the impact of climate change by reducing the carbon footprint of the actual energy system.

However, this energy transition takes time and comes with numerous challenges and hurdles to overcome. It implies a progressive revolution not only from an engineering, infrastructure or technical standpoint, but also in our modern societies.

Moreover, energy production is one of the major sources of greenhouse gas emissions into the atmosphere, and the richest countries are largely responsible for this. At the same time, these countries are the ones that have the economic capability to steer the world toward this transition.

The main challenges in transitioning to sustainable energy are the high upfront costs of renewable energy infrastructure, which can be a barrier for many individuals and businesses. Additionally, there are still limited technological advancements in the energy storage field, which is fundamental to compensate for the inconsistency of the energy supply that renewable sources can provide. Furthermore, there are resistance from fossil fuel industries and policy barriers to renewable energy adoption, such as subsidies and regulations that favor fossil fuels. Overcoming these challenges will require significant investment and policy changes to support the transition to sustainable energy.

Renewable energy sources such as wind, solar or hydroelectric power can significantly help to reduce fossil fuels dependency and provide clean energy [22]. Unfortunately, to date, most of the electricity produced is still generated by burning fossil fuels, but cleaner sources of energy are gaining ground. According to one of the latest UN reports [40] about 29% of electricity currently produced comes from renewable sources, such as wind and solar. Furthermore the cost of renewable-energy technologies also keeps falling, making renewables an increasingly affordable source of power today.

In conclusion, sustainable energy solutions such as renewable sources, energy efficiency measures, and sustainable transportation options are needed to address this crisis and mitigate the impacts of climate change. Wind energy research and the development of new feasible technologies to harness energy from the atmosphere continue to provide significant prospects to support a more sustainable future that is less reliant on fossil fuels.

1.1 Airborne wind energy

Airborne wind energy (AWE) is an emerging technology that aims to harvest wind energy through the use of tethered unmanned aerial vehicles.

As the globe grapples with the recent energy crisis caused by a rise in demand, the increasing concerns of climate change and the need for long-term energy solutions, AWE has emerged as a potential renewable and cost-effective technology that could potentially comply with the world's energy needs while reducing our dependency on fossil fuels.

Figure 1.1: Airborne wind energy system and Wind Turbine altitude operation comparison. [33]

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As shown in Figure 1.1, this technology employs the use of kites, gliders, or drones that are tethered to a ground station and operate at higher altitudes than conventional ground-based wind turbines. The major advantage of this type of technology is the ability to access higher altitudes unlocking a still untouched wind power resource [2]. Compared to winds blowing a few tens of metres above ground level, at greater heights, winds tend to be stronger and more consistent, both onshore and offshore. High-altitude wind is indeed considered as the largest yet untapped source of renewable energy worldwide [2]. In addition to this, AWE technology showcases its remarkable scalability, mobility, and capacity to adjust to various wind conditions. It exhibits exceptional versatility, making it a suitable choice for both onshore and offshore environments, all while demanding minimal infrastructure in comparison to conventional wind turbines. AWE is also a flexible power solution for remote and off-grid regions.

One last considerable and very important advantage is that airborne wind energy systems hold the potential to require less material investment per unit of usable power compared to many other renewable energy sources. This high power-to-mass ratio promises widespread deployment at relatively low costs.

In light of all these remarkable advantages, the development and enhancement of AWE devices have recently become the focus of various companies and research organizations. Their common objective is to establish further AWE as a competitive and economically viable source of renewable energy.

As general rule, these systems can be classified into three distinct categories according to the principle through which energy is extracted from the wind and then converted into electricity [46]:

- **Fly-Gen:** Onboard-generating devices are attached to the airborne element which flies connected to the ground station and during normal operation the tether length is kept constant. While flying crosswind in a circular or figure-of-eight motion, the aerial vehicle converts its kinetic energy into electricity through one or more onboard rotor generators. The power produced is then sent back to the ground station through the tether.
- **Ground-Gen rotary:** These devices fly attached to the ground station, and employ multiple aerofoils which are generally held in the wind by a lifter kite, in modular rotors. To rotate the structure, the rotors are linked together by tethers. Torsion is used for transmitting spinning motion to a ground station generator by maintaining the tethers tight.
- **Ground-Gen pumping:** The most common devices exploit the "pumping" concept to intermittently generate power. The aerial device is connected to the ground station through the tether which is allowed to extend by a turning

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drum. The rotation of the drum is then converted into mechanical power through a generator. A more detailed explanation of the operation of this type of solution is presented in Section 3.1.

Currently, most of the developed prototypes belong to the third listed family as they produce electricity with a fixed ground station (GS) where the traction force in the tether is transformed into electrical power through a generator on the ground. As shown in Figure 1.2 it is possible to further partition AWE concepts into a much more diversified and detailed classification.

Figure 1.2: Classification scheme of different AWE developed concepts. Adapted [36]

Nowadays, prototypes that exploit the concept of crosswind flight are the most common type (some examples are illustrated in Figure 1.3), but tether-aligned and rotational concepts are also under investigation.

Figure 1.3: Example of AWE prototypes operated by: Kitepower, TwingTec, Ampyx Power and Makani Power (from left to right). [37]

1.1.1 Fundamentals of crosswind

The idea of extracting wind power through an airborne system has been investigated since the beginning of the eighties, when Lyod presented the first milestone in this field [29]. From his studies, he determined the maximum amount of power that a tethered wing can harvest from the wind.

An estimate of the theoretical maximum mechanical power P_{max} that a tethered

airfoil can generate is given by

$$P_{max} \leq \frac{2}{27} \rho A v_w^3 C_L \left(\frac{C_L}{C_D} \right)^2 \cos^3 \phi_{el}. \quad (1.1)$$

In this equation, A , C_L and C_D represent the wing area, lift and drag coefficients of the aircraft, while v_w and ρ represent the wind velocity and air density respectively. Furthermore, a non-negligible effect is given by the elevation angle ϕ_{el} , which defines the angle between the wind velocity vector and the vector that connects the ground and aircraft attachment as a straight line. This maximum power value is achieved at a specific apparent airspeed v_a value felt by the kite. This velocity can be attained by adjusting the drag coefficients in case of kites equipped with onboard generators or adjusting the reel-out speed v_{out} of the tether during the traction phase in case of pumping mode operation.

In addition, due to the cubic exponential effect given by the wind velocity in this equation, the ability of airborne wind systems to move in an area where the wind blows stronger, compared to traditional wind turbines, plays an essential role in terms of power extraction possibilities.

1.2 Multi-megawatt AWE systems and simulation

The development and control of Airborne Wind Energy (AWE) systems present an extremely complex challenge to address. In this perspective, the utilization of simulated platforms for testing and running simulations is fundamental. Simulation allows for easier modeling and thorough analysis of AWE systems, including optimization, validation, and safety and efficiency evaluations. The development of safe, certified and efficient control algorithms is amongst the key prerequisites to finally commercialize this new type of technology and compete in the wind power market. Considering that AWE systems are still mainly in a research and prototyping stage, the development of an accurate simulation framework is essential. Virtual environments also provide an appealing strategy for expanding research and testing in this field by avoiding the need for physical manufacturing, which frequently presents significant challenges in terms of costs and time.

In addition, given the goal of further developing actual AWE systems and bringing them up to a Megawatt scale in terms of power production, a simulation system model represents a crucial tool for studying and testing new solutions highlighting possible criticality, potential and limitations in the scalability of this kind of technology.

For this purpose, the idea of creating an open-source simulation framework arose, to be provided to researchers in this field as a suitable tool for testing and further enhancing AWE systems. At a smaller scale, the availability of measurement data from prototype testing allowed the development of some reference dynamic model, as

proposed by Malz et al. in [30] for an optimisation study. At a larger scale instead, a multiphysics engineering model of a megawatt-scale tethered energy kite, named KiteFAST [24], has been developed in support of Makani's energy kite development program with the aim of providing an engineering tool for detailed design and modelling of the aero-hydro-servo-elastic dynamics of an AWE system with electricity generation on the flying device (Fly-Gen) during crosswind flight operation. The simulator models the important physical phenomena and system couplings, including the wind/aerodynamic excitation and full-system dynamics response (fuselage, wings, tail, stabilizers, pylons, nacelles, rotors, tether, ground station, control surfaces, and controller) under both normal or extreme loading conditions.

1.2.1 MegAWES framework

A first version of the framework for a scalable utility-scale multi-megawatt ground-generated airborne wind energy reference system was developed by Eijkelhof in [11]. In this work a detailed representation of the aircraft design inspired by the Ampyx Power AP-3/4, also illustrated in Section 3.4.1, consisting of the platform parameters, material choices and composite layup, is presented and used to create an aeroelastic model of the main wing to analyze its deformation and the flight behavior. A simple modified fixed wing aircraft flight controller was used to fly a circular flight path while the ground station periodically allows the tether to be reeled out and in. A Covariance Matrix Adaptation Evolution Strategy (CMAES) optimisation method was then applied with a specific objective function to find the system design parameters. In [12] further improvements were added that account for the flight dynamics of the fixed-wing aircraft based on a 3 DOFs point mass computational model with a set of pre-calculated aerodynamic force lookup tables. A new discretization of the tether employing five elastic segments was adopted, and a new flight controller was developed by Rapp et al. in [33] to control the wing in pumping cycles, performing figure-of-eight flight maneuvers during reel out of the tether and diving towards the ground station during reel in. In [13] an extension to a six-degrees-of-freedom model is presented along with a study aimed at maximizing the average cycle power under some operational constraints at different wind speeds, in a range from 10 up to 30 m/s. Recently, further enhancements have been made by Hummel in [21] updating the framework with a resized and more realistic inertia and radius winch parameters and a new winch control law to decrease the power production fluctuations during the traction phase. A detailed description is presented in Section 3.7.

Exploiting this simulation platform, the aim of this thesis is to develop a simple and effective flight control system with the final goal of comparing circular and figure-of-eight flight paths.

Chapter 2

Literature Review and Background

In order to establish this technology as a competitive player in the wind energy market, it is essential to develop an autonomous control system that can independently oversee all operational phases, eliminating the need for human intervention. The control of AWE systems encounters similar challenges to those faced by other general autonomous flight systems. These challenges involve achieving specific objectives amidst constant disturbances and unpredictability, while also effectively managing undesirable circumstances.

In the context of large-scale commercial viability, particularly in offshore parks with multiple airborne wind energy systems, also the launching and landing procedures play a pivotal role. However, the AWE community is currently divided, and different approaches for launching and landing are still under development, leading to the publication of several studies that compare various concepts. As the scope of this thesis is not to delve into the intricacies of these phases but rather to concentrate only on the pumping cycle, they will not be extensively addressed.

In the following sections, an in-depth comparison is initially provided between circular and figure-of-eight flight paths as a main research question of this thesis. Subsequently, an overview of the current state-of-the-art of airborne wind energy control design is presented, including an evaluation of general navigation and control system architectures, along with studies related to flight path optimization.

2.1 Research questions

Due to its complex kinematics, controlling and maneuvering a fixed wing tethered kite are some of the biggest challenges for AWE researchers. Tethered aerial vehicles give the possibility of moving three-dimensionally in space, in contrast to the fixed rotational motion of traditional wind turbines where the blades are physically

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constrained around their axis. An autonomous and reliable flight control system is therefore necessary not only to guide the kite along a specific and predefined flight path but also to best adapt the commands and flight operations to the continuous variations in environmental conditions and wind speed.

As will be further discussed in Section 2, there is still no clear evidence demonstrating the optimal flight trajectory for extracting the maximum amount of power from the wind. Numerous studies and research projects have been conducted in this area, but the inconsistencies in the problem formulations, the simplifications adopted to make it more manageable and solvable, as well as the use of many different kite types and technology (leading edge inflatable LEI flexible kite, or rigid wind kite, FlyGen or Ground-Gen pumping typology) prevent the results of these studies from being comparable and, as a result, leave room for uncertainty in the conclusions. In the real world, the inconsistency in the preference for a circular over a figure-of-eight flight path is also apparent considering that several companies within the industry adopt different solutions. During the traction phase some companies like KitePower or Ampyx Power systems adopt a predetermined figure-of-eight flight path while another company like Kitemill follows circular paths while reeling out the tether. For example, Figure 2.1 shows the circular/spiral path flown by the 20 kW kitemill prototype as a result of a 2 hours flight test. Figure 2.2 shows the Kitepower Falcon 100 kW system performing a figure-of-eight flight trajectory.

Figure 2.1: Log data of a 2 hour test while performing circular/spiral flight trajectories during traction phase. [25]

Figure 2.2: Night timelaps of Falcon kite performing figure-of-eight flight trajectories. [44]

Therefore, the primary focus and objectives of this thesis are to develop a relatively easy flight controller for the fixed-wing kite model capable of flying both circular (loops) and figure-of-eight flight paths, as well as to obtain a thorough qualitative and quantitative comparison of the benefits and drawbacks of using each type of trajectory during the traction phase of the pumping cycle. By developing both types of flight paths within the same simulation framework and utilizing identical characteristics for the kite and winch control law, the comparison should yield a more accurate assessment.

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The first fundamental step is to analyze which are the main factors that influence and determine the choice of adopting a figure-of-eight flight path over a circular one. In the scheme illustrated in Figure 2.3 the most relevant factors are shown: control, environmental conditions, type of technology, mechanical limitations, kite type, shape geometry. [19].

Figure 2.3: Scheme representing the main factors that affect the choice of different flight paths during the traction phase of a pumping cycle.

Examining each of these factors individually provides an initial comprehensive understanding and overview of the problem.

The first concept to underline is that the choice of adopting a figure-of-eight flight path compared to a circular one is strongly influenced by the factors illustrated above. However, the ability to adapt the flight path to a specific system or environmental condition may be more relevant than the type of trajectory itself.

Some general considerations can be discussed through a qualitative analysis of the physics of the kite while it flies the two types of path and their impact on the overall system operation and efficiency.

From practical experience, it is evident that there is significant value in considering circular flight paths in AWE systems. What in the kitesurfing sport is called "kite looping" generates a significant amount of pull force. It is intuitively evident that this traction can be readily converted and optimized for power generation. It is also reasonable to surmise that a continuous circular trajectory might be potentially more effective compared to a figure-of-eight pattern. During a loop, the kite follows a circular trajectory without any significant changes in direction, maintaining a relatively constant angle to the wind, and enabling it to preserve its momentum and speed. Indeed, this results in enhanced stability in power generation and reduces the

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amount of inertia to be overcome during maneuvers. It is also effortless to imagine that a circular path, differently from a figure-of-eight path, can access the bottom of the wind window more effectively, maximizing the kite's tether tension, speed and thus the power extracted from the wind.

On the other hand, various considerations may suggest that the optimal flight path is the figure-of-eight pattern. Particularly for this flight course, the direction in which the path is followed is also crucial. In fact, as shown in Figure 2.4, it is possible to identify two figure-of-eight modes, one where the external lobes of the path are flown upwards, which in the continuation of this thesis is called “*figure-of-eight up loop*”, and the other where the lobes are flown downwards towards the ground, “*figure-of-eight down loop*”. Despite the geometric similarity, they have several distinct characteristics.

Figure 2.4: Representation of the circle path on the top and two figure-of-eight modes, flown downwards (left) and upwards (right).

In the “*up loop*” mode, the kite is flying upwards and against the gravitational force when it is placed at the edges of the wind window, which means that the angle with respect to the wind direction is larger and wind power is lower. Instead, in the “*down loop*” mode, the kite is flying up against the gravity in the intersection of the path which is situated in the central region of the wind window where the wind effect is stronger, aiding the sustenance of the flight. In this case, if the path is quite stretched in the horizontal direction, the vertical velocity component of the kite is smaller resulting in a minor slowdown due to the gravity and leading to better low end performances, more constant speed and consequentially lessened peak power generated. This considerations are even more important for “heavy kites” where the much higher mass has a significantly larger effect.

From a purely geometrical point of view another advantage of the figure-of-eight

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path is represented by the significant cosine cubed losses in Equation 1.1. In comparison to a circular geometry, the figure-of-eight shape develops more in a horizontal direction, consequently reducing the variation in the elevation angle in a cycle. This means that the altitude change during the flight is minimized and the power extracted is more constant.

Furthermore, unlike circular paths, figure-of-eight patterns necessitate continuous changes in the flight direction, potentially leading to speed reductions and, consequently, lower power generation. These directional alterations could result in efficiency losses.

Approaching the problem from a control standpoint, a circular path, due to its singular and consistent direction of motion, may require a simpler control algorithm. Nevertheless, it is essential to underline that both patterns present significant challenges, and the majority of path-following algorithms discussed in Section 2.2 are based on the same fundamental concept and architecture. Consequently, a system capable of executing continuous loops should, theoretically, be equipped to handle figure-of-eight paths as well. This operational flexibility could be advantageous for coping with variable wind conditions. In addition, the extra required inputs to the controlled surfaces to steer the kite along a figure-of-eight trajectory as opposed to a circular path could potentially impact and diminish the aerodynamic efficiency of the latter.

Another relevant factor in the optimal flight analysis is the type of kite adopted and its dynamic performances. To extract the maximum power from the wind maintaining a higher travelling speed is crucial as even minor increases in velocity can lead to significant rise in power output. So comes into play the agility, maneuverability and aerodynamic efficiency to generate the required amount of lift. This might suggest that an optimal flight path for a quicker fixed-wing kite might not be as optimal for a slower LEI soft kite. In connection with this, it is also important to highlight the challenge of scaling this systems up to a multi-megawatt level: with bigger and heavier kites, the increase in mass and inertia has a non-negligible impact on the dynamics and agility of the kite, thereby influencing the possible solutions of optimal flight path problem.

Particular considerations may also arise concerning the type of technology. The weight contribution of the tether, particularly in AWEs based on Fly-Gen that make use of onboard generators and heavier conductive lines compared to Ground-Gen family, may impact the choice of flight path adopted. In such instances, employing a circular path or a figure-of-eight maneuver may provide notable benefits by enabling more efficient management of the tether's weight.

Linked to this, there are also certain mechanical limitations and practical considerations that must not be underestimated. One such example is the twisting effect of

the tether caused by continuous looping of the kite in the same direction. It is important to note that the figure-of-eight path remains unaffected by this issue. This is because during the course of flight, each lobe of the path is flown with a change in the direction of rotation, resulting in the untwisting of the tether. However, in the circular path this problem might be still overcome simply by alternating loop directions between pumping cycles or by adding an untwisting tether attachment system on the kite. In the case of Fly-Gen systems, circular patterns require an auxiliary element as a rotary union in the tether to allow the electric power transmission from the kite to the ground.

In some particular environmental conditions, one of the two paths may be more effective or capable of better handling wind gusts and turbulence or extremely low or high wind speed situations. In low wind conditions a figure-of-eight path may provide enhanced performance given that this flight path efficiently “pumps” the kite, creating a continuous push and pull effect, which allows the kite to remain airborne and in motion even when the natural wind force is minimal. On the other hand a circular path, due to its simplicity, might provide better performance in handling higher and gusty wind conditions.

Lastly, the factor to be considered in this analysis is the land area covered by flying the two types of path. Considering an equal range of tether length, given its elongated horizontal development the shape of the figure-of-eight pattern requires more space with respect to a circular and more compact spiral path. Considering the deployment of a single airborne system in a remote location, this may not be considered a problem, as the underlying portion of land can be used for other purposes. Instead the sensitivity to the area spent flying is considerably much more relevant when it extends to the concept of wind farms, where several systems work close to each other. The choice of the flight path might affect wind farm density and as a result a higher or lower amount of power production per unit of land covered.

2.2 Control and navigation of tethered kite

In general, an autonomous flight control system is achieved through a hierarchical control structure as commonly proposed in [34] [43] for Ground-Gen rigid-wing AWE system. This cascaded approaches present an effective strategy for splitting the complex problem of controlling AWE systems into smaller and more manageable sub-problems.

The conventional control architecture design shown in Figure 2.5 is composed of several levels, with a higher external layer in charge of slower control and decision-making. This level is frequently depicted as a state machine that states the current operating mode. The fast system dynamics, which include interactions with the environment, state measurements, and actuation, and require rapid responses are

instead managed by a faster internal control loop.

Figure 2.5: Classical control architecture representation, with outer and inner control loops, of a ground-gen AWE system.

The benefit of such a hierarchical or cascading structure is that each layer may be customized optimally while still adhering to the interfaces of the surrounding layers. This strategy is especially important if the operating modes diverge considerably as in this case of study.

The finite state machine takes the role of the system supervisor, triggering transitions across various flight operations, including launch, traction and retraction phases, landing procedures, as well as evasive or safety maneuvers in response to anomaly and fault detections.

In order to harness and optimize the maximum potential of wind power, a guidance system is essential, enabling precise control to lead the kite along a predefined path. Designing an outer loop with periodic guidance to steer a kite properly is therefore the first essential control problem to solve. As presented in Section 2.1, during the traction phase the kite must be guided over a spherical surface (flight sphere) following circular (loops) or figure-of-eight flight path. In the literature, this problem is commonly faced using target point based approaches. Fagiano et al. in [15] demonstrate the feasibility of the concept achieving periodic figure-of-eight flight paths by alternating two target points. In [16] Fechner et al. present a technique utilizing four waypoints interconnected by arcs and great circles to refine the figure-of-eight flight pattern.

An issue with the two or four waypoint-based approaches is that they yield a less predictable and not well defined path shape, which would lead to a suboptimal and less controllable performance in terms of power production. Nevertheless, their simplicity makes them readily implementable and computationally efficient, rendering them appealing in practical applications.

In these studies, the concept of the target point is employed for flexible or soft wings, where the turn rate law, presented by Erhard and Strauch [14], is applicable. This principle links the kite response to the steering deflection commands showing a proportionality between the tangential plane course rate (turn rate to follow a reference

path) and the kite steering input. Conversely, fixed-wings, being essentially tethered aircraft, employ standard actuation systems such as ailerons, rudder, and elevator. As a result, this law does not apply in their case.

Exploiting a similar and more developed control strategy, an earlier version of Ampyx Power flight controller is presented by Ruiterkamp et al. [35]. In this case, the longitudinal and lateral motion of the kite are decoupled to be independently designed and controlled through a simple control scheme. The approach to address the path following problem involves breaking down a continuous figure-of-eight curve into a sequence of discrete target points. Subsequently, the desired direction is determined using a look-ahead distance, which identifies the appropriate target point on the path and two simple linear controllers are then used to convert it into a reference roll/bank angle relative to the tangential plane. The longitudinal motion constrained by the tether is controlled by the reel-out speed of the winch and a fixed elevator setting, similar to the one used for flexible wings, is adopted to fly at a high lift-to-drag ratio and generate the maximum amount of power. This solution was found not to be particularly effective in ensuring that the tether tension does not exceed its limit value.

Another popular non linear path following strategy frequently used in the navigation algorithm of aerial vehicles is the so called L_1 guidance logic. Initially proposed by Park et al. in 2004 [31] and later revised by Fernandes, Vinha, Paiva in 2022 [18] in their " L_0 " variation, this solution has proven to guarantee asymptotic stability and to be more effective than most common proportional controllers, as well as suited for airborne wind energy systems. This logic is based on the calculation of the desired centripetal acceleration, given the mass and lift force that is generated, to define a reference roll angle that enables reaching a specific target point at a predefined look-ahead distance. A high-level description of this strategy is proposed in Section 4.1, as it is the control navigation concept adopted in the development of this thesis. The L_1 non-linear guidance strategy is also employed by Fernandes et al. (2018) in [17] to formulate their trajectory controller for AWEs, incorporating the ability to handle wind gusts. Continuous path parametrization is also widely adopted since presented by Jehle et al. in [23] and further applied by Rapp, Schmehl, Oland, and Haas [34] for rigid-wing kite control, making use of a PID controller for the current state-ideal path error and a non linear dynamic inversion to obtain the desired attitude of the kite. The same approach is also applied in [33] where required course and path angle rates $\dot{\chi}_{k,c}$ and $\dot{\gamma}_{k,c}$ are determined based on a continuous figure-of-eight path parametrization during the traction phase, and an inner and outer control loop are used for the determination of the actuator input and required roll, pitch and yaw angles respectively. In [27] Haocheng Li et al. focus on accurate modeling of the AWE system, developing a Lyapunov-based controller designed to control the attitude of the kite and rate error dynamics. Translational and rotational motions are managed independently using differential and proportional control laws.

2.3 Flight path optimization approaches

The problem of flight path optimization and the development of algorithms that maximize power output are fundamental in the AWE literature. Since the first crosswind study presented by Loyd in [29] and discussed in Section 1.1.1, varying fidelity analytical dynamic models have been used to investigate optimal flight trajectories and assess their performance in approaching the theoretical limits while respecting several physical constraints and restrictions.

To achieve this goal, several techniques have been proposed in the literature, ranging from both online and offline optimal control problems, model predictive control (MPC), and online adaptive control approaches, as well as iterative or reinforcement learning techniques.

Offline optimization provides a systematic method for predicting the projected power output of a specific AWE system for a given wind speed profile or simply a wind speed distribution at a given location. As a result, it is possible to estimate the predicted power production while taking into account the physical dynamic constraints. On the other hand, in the context of offline optimal control problems, the effectiveness of the solutions is greatly influenced by the accuracy and quality of the system model that is used.

Under certain hypotheses which allow the problem to be simplified, low-fidelity models proved to be acceptable and low-computing approaches to address the optimum trajectories problem of AWEs.

To evaluate optimal trajectories, in particular to study circular paths for Fly-Gen AWESs, in [39] Trevisi et al. (2020) propose a simplified low-fidelity quasi-analytical model approach facing the problem in the frequency domain, making use of harmonic balance method instead of solving the dynamic and optimal control problem in the time domain. The developed flight simulator is used to analyze various trajectories and production strategies, thereby deriving analytical expressions.

An experimentally validated ground-gen system dynamic model is used by Licitra et al. [28] to solve an optimal control problem, showing that, when subjected to certain prescribed constraints, circular and figure-of-eight trajectories yield comparable mean power. In [1] a specifically designed toolbox for Airborne Wind Energy systems is also presented, with a focus on modeling, optimizing, and controlling multiple-kite systems. Its key features include streamlining tasks related to system dynamics generation, optimal control problem formulation, trajectory optimization, postprocessing, visualization, and tracking MPC design for offline closed-loop simulations. This tool is also used by Leuthold et al. [26] to investigate power-optimal trajectories by solving a series of optimal control problems for a Multiple-kite airborne wind energy systems (MAWES). In [9] Diwale et al. investigate optimal flight

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paths for flexible tether airfoil using Gaussian Processes to effectively learn the relationship between the controller set points and both the objective and constraint functions and maximize the generated towing forces.

For autonomous AWE systems, alongside offline optimization, several studies focus on an online path planning optimization approach such as Nonlinear Model Predictive Control (NMPC). In [7] and [8] Diehl et al. (2004) apply the method for a nonlinear unstable ODE system represented by a dual line kite design for flying periodical loops, showing significantly improved performances compared to a previously developed LQR controller. In addition, in [6] Cobb et al. present an iterative learning approach for optimizing the course geometry in repetitive path following applications, with the goal to maximize the average power output over a figure-of-eight path. Following this iterative approach, the algorithm performs adaptive adjustments to the trajectory shape to optimize performance and improve power output.

Chapter 3

Framework and models

This chapter provides an illustration and description of the models included in the simulation framework. It begins with an overview of the general simulation flow and the reference systems that have been adopted. Then, the characteristics of the kite layout, along with its associated aerodynamic model and the wind shear model, are discussed. Lastly, the tether and the functioning of the ground station and winch control system are explained.

3.1 Problem definition

The first fundamental challenge that needs to be tackled is to design a controller loop that guides the kite in a periodic manner on a spherical surface (tangential direction control objective).

In the case of this study, the system leverages the ground-gen concept, wherein the aerodynamic force acting on the aircraft is harnessed to generate tether tension. This tension, in turn, impels the unwinding of a tether from a drum, which drives a generator. Consequently, the mechanical torque produced is converted into electrical power on the ground. To perform a complete pumping cycle, the flight controller is required to effectively manage the kite during both operational modes, traction and retraction phases, also shown in Figure 3.1. During the traction phase the kite is driven along a predefined circular or figure-of-eight flight path in a periodic manner, pulling and reeling out the tether from the drum until the maximum length is reached. It encompasses a retraction phase during which the kite glides back, usually following a straight or arc trajectory, towards the ground station, and a portion of the generated energy is utilized to rewind the tether onto the winch drum. Between the two modes a short transition phase is needed to lower the tether tension and switch from crosswind flight to “standard” one and vice versa. The cycle commences anew once the minimum tether length is attained. These two combined modes constitute what is commonly called *pumping cycle*.

Figure 3.1: Illustration of the pumping cycle concept, traction and retraction phases. Adapted from [33].

Due to its relative simplicity of implementation and demonstrated functionality to design the flight controller, a similar approach to the one developed by Empyx Power, presented in Section 2.2, is used also for this case of study.

3.2 Simulation of the computational model

In the following, a brief description of the simulation framework, also introduced in Section 1.2.1, and each of its sub-components used in this work is presented. The starting base is the simulation framework developed in [11] in a Matlab-Simulink environment, which has been modified and adapted with the new flight controller block, new winch controller law and the tether and wind profile model also used in the further updated version of MegAWEs framework [10]. In order to visualize the flow of the simulation through each sub-block of the framework, a schematic illustration is shown in Figure 3.2. The initial step involves setting up the model in Matlab, followed by the transition to the Simulink environment. In this beginning phase the state variables such as velocity, position and attitude of the kite and starting tether shape and tension are initialized. The set of all these variables constitutes the flight state vector $\vec{\mathbf{X}}$. The vector $\vec{\mathbf{y}}$ instead contains the kinetic and angular velocity of the kite around its center of gravity. The system can be then described by a time derivative of the dynamic state vector where \mathbf{M} represents the generalised mass matrix and $\vec{\mathbf{F}}$ the generalised force vector:

$$\mathbf{M}\dot{\vec{\mathbf{y}}} = \vec{\mathbf{F}}. \quad (3.1)$$

The state and dynamic vectors are passed to the flight controller, which computes the desired flight path, as well as the required actuation and control input \mathbf{C}_{act} , \mathbf{C}_T for the kite and for the winch controller into the ground station block. Based on the tether tension and reel-out speed, this block determines also the mechanical power

3.2. SIMULATION OF THE COMPUTATIONAL MODEL

produced and consumed during traction and retraction phases. In Section 3.7 a detailed description of the winch parameters and control law utilized is presented.

Figure 3.2: Simulation framework structure for the computational model. [13]

The state vector \vec{X} and control acuation \mathbf{C}_T are also passed to the aerodynamic module, described in detail in Section 3.4.2, which is responsible for determining the forces \mathbf{F}_a and moments \mathbf{M}_a acting on the aircraft by using either a Fluid–structure interaction (FSI) algorithm or precomputed look-up tables. The state vector is also sent into a wind shear model block, described in Section 3.5, which, based on the defined wind velocity, computes the air speed around each particle of the tether $\mathbf{p}_{z,t}$, $\mathbf{v}_{z,t}$ and on the kite $\mathbf{v}_{w,k}$. At each time step, the time integration block computes numerically the integration over time of the system state variables with a constant time step of 0.01 s, the flight state is updated and next iteration is initialised until either the maximum simulation time or convergence is reached, and simulation is stopped.

3.3 Reference systems

To model all the systems and effectively represent the many vector quantities that are involved, various reference systems are used. In most cases, these coordinate frames align with those commonly used in the flight mechanics literature, but some other are especially introduced for the AWE domain. This section presents a description and graphical representation of the reference frames used throughout this thesis.

Earth and wind reference frames

In Figure 3.3 the earth and wind reference frames are presented. The wind reference frame has the x-axis point aligned with the wind direction vector $w_{d,e}$ which is previously defined in the earth reference system. In the case of study, the earth reference frame is defined as a right-handed system with the ground station placed in the origin and the z-axis pointing into the ground. This definition is coherent with the usual one defined in the aerospace literature which is also implemented in the aerospace simulink block of the simulation framework.

Figure 3.3: Earth and wind reference frames.

Tangential and body coordinate systems

To guide the kite through the wind window and to define the desired flight path for the traction phase it is convenient to define a reference frame centered in the kite position and tangential to the flight sphere. This frame, shown in Figure 3.4, can be obtained through a sequence of transformation matrices starting from the wind coordinate system. More to the point, first a rotation of θ_{az} around z_w , followed by a rotation around the new y' of elevation angle ϕ_{el} and a translation along x'' of a distance equal to the radial position of the kite. Finally, by adjusting the direction of the axes the North-East-Down (NED) coordinate system is obtained corresponding to x_τ, y_τ, z_τ respectively.

Figure 3.4: Wind and τ reference systems, visualization of azimuthal θ_{az} and elevation ϕ_{el} angle and tangent plane to the wind sphere in the kite position. On the left a detail shows the body-fixed coordinate system.

Figure 3.4 also shows the body coordinate system which is fixed in both origin and orientation to the kite. In this case of study the kite is considered rigid and any deflection or deformation are not taken into account. In particular the body-fixed frame is centered and oriented along with the main wing, so that the x_B axis points through the nose of the aircraft, the y_B axis points to the right side of the main wing perpendicular to x_B and the z_B points down through the bottom side of the aircraft orthogonally to the x - y plane.

Position and attitude parametrization

The position of the kite, usually referred to the wind or earth reference frame can be described by the position vector

$$\vec{p}_{k,w} = \begin{bmatrix} x_w \\ y_w \\ z_w \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} R \cos(\theta_{az}) \cos(\phi_{el}) \\ R \cos(\theta_{az}) \sin(\phi_{el}) \\ R \sin(\phi_{el}) \end{bmatrix} \quad (3.2)$$

expressed both in cartesian or polar coordinates.

To describe and simulate the kite attitude in the space, a conventional Euler angles parametrization is used. By defining a sequence of rotation matrices around Z, Y, X axes that represent *yaw, pitch* and *roll* rotation of angles ψ, θ, ϕ respectively, it is possible to define the orientation of the body fixed frame with respect to the earth coordinate system:

$$R_{EB} = R_z(\psi)R_y(\theta)R_x(\phi) \quad (3.3)$$

$$R_{EB} = \begin{bmatrix} \cos \psi \cos \theta & \cos \psi \sin \theta \sin \phi - \sin \psi \cos \phi & \cos \psi \sin \theta \cos \phi - \sin \psi \sin \phi \\ \sin \psi \cos \theta & \sin \psi \sin \theta \sin \phi + \cos \psi \cos \phi & \sin \psi \sin \theta \cos \phi - \cos \psi \sin \phi \\ -\sin \theta & \cos \theta \sin \phi & \cos \theta \cos \phi \end{bmatrix} \quad (3.4)$$

Aerodynamic coordinate system

Finally, to determine the aerodynamic forces that act on the aircraft, it is also useful to define an aerodynamic system of coordinates attached to the kite body and with the origin coinciding with the body-fixed frame one. Due to the non-negligible effect of the wind velocity it is possible to define the apparent wind velocity v_a , where v_w and v_k represent the actual wind and kinematic velocity expressed in the inertial earth reference frame:

$$\mathbf{v}_{a,e} = \mathbf{v}_{k,e} - \mathbf{v}_{w,e} \quad \mathbf{v}_{k,e} = \dot{\mathbf{p}} \quad (3.5)$$

By usual convention, the aerodynamic frame, shown in Figure 3.5, is defined so that the flow is in the positive x-axis direction, which means that this axis is pointing in the same direction as the relative flow velocity vector at the aircraft (apparent wind velocity).

The relation between the bodyfixed reference frame and the aerodynamic coordinate system allows to define the angle of attack (AoA) α_a and sideslip angle β_a .

Figure 3.5: Aerodynamic coordinate system and bodyfixed reference frame, definition of angle of attack α_a and sideslip angle β_a . Adapted from [11].

3.4 Fixed-wing kite model

This section proposes the fixed-wing kite dynamic model with the corresponding equations of motion. Furthermore, a brief description of the kite-model layout used in the simulation framework is presented.

Equations of motion

To model and simulate the flight dynamics, the kite is modeled using generic six-degrees of freedom (6-DoFs) rigid body equations of motion assuming a flat and non rotating earth system (Coriolis effect can be considered negligible).

The total vector of forces acting on the kite is then composed of the resulting aerodynamic force \vec{F}_a , the tether force \vec{F}_t , and the weight or gravitational force \vec{F}_g . More in detail, the resulting aerodynamic force is

$$\vec{F}_{a,b} = \frac{1}{2} \rho S_{ref} v_a^2 \begin{pmatrix} C_x \\ C_y \\ C_z \end{pmatrix} \quad (3.6)$$

and will be investigated deeply in the aerodynamic model section. More in detail the weight force vector in the body-fixed frame is defined as

$$\vec{F}_{g,b} = R_{BE} \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ mg \end{pmatrix} \quad (3.7)$$

where R_{BE} represents the transformation matrix from the body to the earth reference system where g is defined as the constant gravitational acceleration.

Therefore the total force vector is the sum of forces acting on the kite:

$$\vec{F}_{tot} = \vec{F}_a + \vec{F}_g + \vec{F}_t. \quad (3.8)$$

The translational equations of motion of the kite expressed in the body-fixed reference frame are

$$\vec{\dot{v}}_b = \begin{bmatrix} \dot{u}_b \\ \dot{v}_b \\ \dot{w}_b \end{bmatrix} = \frac{\vec{F}_{tot}}{m} - \vec{w}_b \times \vec{v}_b = \frac{\vec{F}_a + \vec{F}_g + \vec{F}_t}{m} - \vec{w}_b \times \vec{v}_b \quad (3.9)$$

The rotational dynamic equation is:

$$\vec{\dot{w}}_b = \begin{bmatrix} \dot{p}_b \\ \dot{q}_b \\ \dot{r}_b \end{bmatrix} = J_b^{-1}(\vec{M}_b - \vec{w}_b \times (J_b \vec{w})) \quad (3.10)$$

where M_b is the sum of the moments acting on the kite and J_b represents the inertia tensor matrix of the kite. The roll, pitch and yaw rate are defined by p_b , q_b and r_b . The angular velocities in the body fixed reference frame by multiplying a transformation matrix with the angular velocities in the inertial reference frame.

3.4.1 Fixed wing kite layout

For the developed simulation framework a fixed-wing kite layout has been designed by Eijkelhof in [11], where a detailed description is presented. In Figure 3.6 an illustration of the proposed kite model is depicted. The design is based on an upscaled version of the AP-3 model of Ampyx Power up to an approximated wing area of 150 m^2 . Based on this value, a wing span of around 43 m , aspect ratio, and all other structure parameters are determined.

The kite structure is composed of a twin-fuselage configuration which permits to split the required propulsion power over two propellers placed in front of each fuselage while enhances an adequate tether clearance throughout launching and landing

3.4. FIXED-WING KITE MODEL

phases. The single tether is attached as close to the center of gravity as possible, under the main wing.

Due to its configuration, each fuselage section has a rudder and the two parts are connected by a single horizontal stabilizer (elevator). The layout also includes ailerons as additional control surfaces, that extend from 60% to 90% of the half-span of the main wing.

Figure 3.6: Top view of the fixed-wing kite layout used in the simulation framework with some of the main geometrical quantities. Image from [11].

Table 3.1 lists the main wing, tail and fuselage geometrical parameters of the kite used in the simulation framework.

Table 3.1: List of general parameters of the proposed kite layout. [11]

Parameter	Value	Unit
Center of gravity	-1.67,0,0.229	m,m,m
Inertia J_{xx}	5.7680×10^5	kg m^2
Inertia J_{yy}	0.8107×10^5	kg m^2
Inertia J_{zz}	6.5002×10^5	kg m^2
Total mass	6885.2	kg
<i>Wing:</i>		
Span	42.47	m
$Chord_{root}$	4.46	m
$Chord_{root}$	2.11	m
LE sweep	2	-
Aspect ratio	12.0	-
Surface area	150.45	m^2
$Air\ foil_{root}$	$RevE_{HC}$	
$Air\ foil_{root}$	$RevE_{HC}$	
<i>Horizontal tail/Elevator:</i>		
Span	7.6	m
Chord	2.8	m
Airfoil	NACA 0012	
<i>Vertical tail/Rudder:</i>		
Span	3	m
Chord	2.8	m
Airfoil	NACA 0012	
<i>Fuselages:</i>		
Length	20	m
Radius	0.6	m
$X_{NOSE-LE_{wing}}$	6.5	m
$Y_{Root-Fuselage}$	3.8	m

3.4.2 Aerodynamic model

In contrast to the complexities inherent in higher-level soft-wing aerodynamic models, the aerodynamic behavior of a rigid-wing kite is significantly more predictable and accessible to modeling. The structural stiffness of the kite wing provides an additional stability to its aerodynamic performance, allowing for a more straightforward analytical approach and producing results that are easier to grasp and implement in real circumstances.

To model and determine the behaviour of the kite, the aerodynamic properties are initially determined by using the Fluid–structure interaction (FSI) model algorithm, which consist of a three dimensional structural finite element model coupled with a potential-flow based panel method. A detailed description of the method is presented in [11]. Utilizing this strategy, the main wing has been analyzed three-

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dimensionally from a minimum to a maximum angle of attack α_a , defined as in Section 3.3, considering merely the linear region of the lift-AoA curve. For simplicity, the curve is truncated to only the linear part: consequentially the stall behavior of the kite is not observable. In Figure 3.7 the main wing aerodynamic coefficients C_L , C_D and C_M are depicted in relation to the angle of attack.

Figure 3.7: Pre-computed aerodynamic coefficients, from top, lift, drag and pitch moment coefficient versus angle of attack. [13]

In this case of study, for simplicity and to lower the computational cost, the aerodynamic forces and moments are determined making use of the precomputed static aerodynamic coefficients. This strategy is also employed to model the aerodynamic properties of the elevator and the rudder, as depicted in Figure 3.8. However, in this case these coefficients are not determined by the FSI algorithm but making use of Rfoil (a specific software tool for designing and analyzing airfoils). The impact of the airflow around the fuselages is considered negligible, but their shapes are nonetheless taken into account when defining the total center of gravity of the structure.

Figure 3.8: Pre-computed lift and drag aerodynamic coefficients versus angle of attack. [13]

3.5 Wind shear model

One of the main reasons why airborne wind energy systems are promising is the possibility of reaching higher altitude, compared to standard wind turbines, and to harness the full potential of the high-altitude winds that blow stronger and more consistently. In the study of AWE systems, for an accurate power production prediction, it is therefore necessary to accurately and faithfully model the wind patterns that represent how wind velocity changes with altitude.

A common assumption in conventional wind energy applications is a logarithmic wind speed profile [4] which expresses wind speed as a function of the altitude h :

$$v_w(h) = v_{w,ref} \frac{\ln\left(\frac{h}{z_0}\right)}{\ln\left(\frac{h_{ref}}{z_0}\right)} \quad (3.11)$$

In this formula $v_{w,ref}$ represents the measured wind speed at a reference height h_{ref} , usually of about 6 m, and z_0 is a factor that depends on the land surfaces type. Given the increasing logarithmic trend this profile is not suitable and realistic for high altitudes where AWEs tend to operate. Above an altitude of 200 m this wind distribution is no longer valid and more realistic representations must be considered to ensure accurate results.

To accomplish this, in the simulation framework a measured profile is adopted to represent the wind speed variation. Some measured data profiles, both off-shore

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and on-shore, are available thanks to Ijmuiden and Cabauw wind measurement tower. On these meteorological masts sensors are placed at various heights to observe and record wind speed direction and speed and a LIDAR laser technology allows to extend the measured field up to 600 m of altitude. Considering the average wind profile and maximum measured wind speed a normalised curve for offshore (Ijmuiden) and onshore (Cabauw) is obtained and thus scalable for each operational wind speed of the power curve. A comparison between the described wind shear models is shown in Figure 3.9. In this plot a wind velocity reference $v_{w,ref}$ of 6 m/s is used in the logarithmic profile, while a $v_{w,sca}$ of 15 is applied as scale factor for the Cabauw and Ijmuiden curves, to obtain a similar wind velocity at 10 m above the ground and highlight the different trends of wind shear models.

Figure 3.9: Comparison of different wind shear proposed: Cabauw, Ijmuiden and logarithmic profile, showing wind speed value at different altitudes.

As it is visible from the graphs, the offshore wind profile is varying less with altitude compared to the onshore one, where the presence of the ground hinders the lower air layers closer to it and generates a less uniform distribution and consequently a higher wind velocity gradient. After the altitude in which the Ijmuiden and Cabauw curves reach their maximum value, the wind velocity can be reasonably assumed as constant, as the interaction with the ground is considered negligible above the atmospheric boundary layer.

Unlike the two measured curves, the logarithmic profile exhibits a continuous upward trend without ever reaching a saturation value.

In the continuation of this thesis only the Ijmuiden wind profile is adopted.

3.6 Tether model

Here is a brief summary of the tether modeling approach employed and developed in [13] which is also adopted in this thesis.

In the literature, different methods to model the tether dynamic are proposed. Based on [45] a static lumped-mass tether model is chosen to simulate a stiff Dyneema® tether while maintaining a feasible simulation time step. By using this approach elastic vibrations are disregarded to simplify the model.

The quasi-static method computes the steady-state configuration and tension forces along the tether using a shooting process from the ground station to the kite, and the final shape of the tether is then given by an equilibrium between centrifugal forces, gravity, and drag. In Figure 3.10 tether model discretization and particles equilibrium are shown. A Trust-Region Dogleg Method implemented by MathWorks Inc. in Matlab R2019B adjusts the tether force iteratively until it coincides with the kite position with an error order of magnitude less than 10^{-6} . The state vector can be written as $[\theta_n, \varphi_n, T_n]^T$ with the tension force on the ground station side expressed in the wind reference frame given by $\mathbf{T}_n = T_n[\sin(\theta_n) \cos(\varphi_n), \sin(\varphi_n), \cos(\theta_n) \cos(\varphi_n)]^T$. In this case spherical coordinates are adopted for the stability of the method, allowing a positive force magnitude and arbitrary direction, ensuring rapid convergence.

Figure 3.10: Tether model, mass discretization and force equilibrium of particles. [13]

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The equations of motion of the particle tether model are then given by

$$m_j \cdot \ddot{\mathbf{p}}_j = \mathbf{T}_{j-1} - \mathbf{T}_j - \mathbf{F}_j^g + \mathbf{F}_j^d \quad (3.12)$$

$$\ddot{\mathbf{p}}_j = \left(\frac{p_{kite}}{\|p_{kite}\|^2} \times v_{kite} \right) \times \left[\left(\frac{p_{kite}}{\|p_{kite}\|^2} \times v_{kite} \right) \times p_j \right] \quad (3.13)$$

where $\ddot{\mathbf{p}}_j$ represents the acceleration of the particle, while \mathbf{F}_j^d and \mathbf{F}_j^g , expressed as

$$\mathbf{F}_j^g = [0, 0, m_j g]^T \quad (3.14)$$

$$\mathbf{F}_j^d = -\frac{1}{2} \rho_t L_j \cdot d \cdot C_N \cdot \|v_j^n v_j^t\| \quad (3.15)$$

represent the drag and gravitational forces component acting on each j th mass element respectively. p_{kite} and v_{kite} represent instead respectively the position and velocity of the kite, C_N the normal drag coefficient of a cylindrical tether, ρ_t the linear density and L_j the unstrained segment length. Furthermore v_j^r is the relative wind velocity at each segment and v_j^n and v_j^t are its normal and tangent component

$$v_j^t = \left(\frac{p_{j-1} - p_j}{\|p_{j-1} - p_j\|} \cdot v_j^r \right) \frac{p_{j-1} - p_j}{\|p_{j-1} - p_j\|} \quad (3.16)$$

$$v_j^n := v_j^r - v_j^t \quad (3.17)$$

$$v_j^r = v_j - \mathbf{V}_{w,j} \quad (3.18)$$

$\mathbf{V}_{w,j}$ represents the wind speed at each particle height.

Table 3.2 shows all the detailed physical parameters of the tether considered in the simulation

Table 3.2: Tether physical parameters used in the simulation. [13]

Parameter	Value	Unit
Diameter (d)	0.0297	m
Linear density (ρ_t)	0.6729	kg m^{-1}
Normal drag coefficient (C_N)	1.2	-
Axial elastic modulus (E)	$116 \cdot 10^9$	GPa
Number of masses (N_p)	15	-

3.7 Ground station and winch control

In the following, a brief description of the modeling and design of the winch controller used in the simulation framework is presented. The proposed winch control strategy has been developed by Hummel in [21].

The winch comprises a drum around which the rope is coiled, along with an energy conversion system. The winch is modeled as a single rotating body and has an inertia J , radius r , and viscous friction moment modeled as linear functions of rotational speed. By utilizing these parameters, the modeling analysis remains valid and applicable to various types of winches, including those with electrical, hydraulic, or mechanical drivetrains. In this case the inertia J refers to the entire drivetrain and the radius of the drum is assumed constant throughout the winding and unwinding phases of the tether. For an in-depth understanding of parameter selection, refer to [21]. Table 3.3 lists the winch controller and physical parameters adopted in the simulation.

Table 3.3: Winch parameters used in the simulation.

Parameter	Value	Unit
Winch radius r	1.5	m
Winch inertia J	10000	kg m^{-1}
Friction	10	-
Acceleration max	± 5	m/s^2
Velocity max	± 25	m/s
Winch gain k_p	10	-
Winch gain k_i	35	-

Torque control - Traction strategy

To model the winch, three acting moments are considered: the rotational moment given by the pulling force of the tether F_t multiplied by the drum radius, a friction torque and a winch torque control τ . Based on the equilibrium of these three moments, a torque control input can be computed to control the tether tension. The tether force generated by a cross-wind flying system with S wing surface area and lift-to-drag ratio L/D is given by the quasi-steady model equation

$$F_t = \frac{1}{2}\rho v_w^2 S C_R \left(1 + \left(\frac{L}{D} \right)^2 \right) (1 - f)^2 = \mathcal{C}(v_w - v_r)^2 \quad (3.19)$$

In the formula, ρ represent the air density, v_w the wind speed, C_R a resultant force coefficient and f the reel-out factor. Main performance parameters of the kite are collected in \mathcal{C} :

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$$\mathcal{C} = \frac{1}{2}\rho S C_R \left(1 + \left(\frac{L}{D} \right)^2 \right) \quad (3.20)$$

Given these expressions, and by choosing a reel-out factor of 1/3 as the optimal value for wind power generation considered in Section 1.1.1, an optimal tether force curve can be defined as a function of reel-out speed:

$$\tau = 4 \mathcal{C} v_r^2 r \quad (3.21)$$

The graphical representation of the optimal tether force curve is shown in Figure 3.11.

Figure 3.11: Optimal tether force vs reel-out speed curve, given a reel-out factor of 1/3. [21]

The optimal reel-out factor previously determined is independent of the wind speed, however in some particular high wind speed conditions the system may reach its nominal (or maximum) power in which both the tether tension and reel-out speed cannot be increased further and must be kept constant. As a design choice the tether force limit and power limit coincide on the winch control curve so that given a tether tension limit of $1.39 \cdot 10^6$ N the upper limit for power generation can be computed as:

$$P_{\max} = F_{t\max} \cdot v_{r,F_{t\max}} = F_{t\max} \cdot \sqrt{\frac{F_{t\max}}{4\mathcal{C}}} \quad (3.22)$$

and results to be of around 9.3 MW. Over this limit, the winch is out of its range of control and it will tend to stay at this point even if the wind speed increases. In this case, to prevent an over strain in the tether, the kite flight control system

intervenes by limiting the aerodynamic performances of the kite, for example by properly adjusting the angle of attack α_a . This condition is not taken into account in this work since the flight control tends to fly the kite always at its maximum performances during the traction phase as will be described in Section 4.2.1.

On the other hand, especially in low wind condition, the strategy proposed so far does not guarantee that the kite is always able to fly the ascent part of both circular and figure of eight paths. In this scenario, a minimum tether force is needed and the winch control ought to reel-in by consuming a part of the energy, so that a minimal tension is induced.

To recap, during the traction phase, the winch controller computes the optimal tether force based on the actual reel-out speed, in such a way that the combination of reelout speed and tether force lies on the optimal curve, and tries to track it always ensuring a minimum tension in the tether. During the retraction phase instead, no optimal tether tension is calculated and the winch controller simply tracks a predefined force setpoint defined empirically like in the controller developed by Rapp et al. [33] adopted in MegAWES.

Control loop

Due to the presence of two distinct regions in the reference tether force, a minimum and constant region and a quadratically varying force with reel-out speed, the design of two controllers is needed. In [21], the quasi-steady model of the kite has been linearised around an operating point around which the attainment of the minimum tether force is the most probable. A minimum tether force value of $0.5 \cdot 10^6$ N is so obtained and used as a trim condition.

In order to maintain the system at the minimum tether force, a PI controller has been developed. By applying torque to the winch, the reel-out speed can be adjusted. Knowing the transfer function from the torque control input τ to F_t and how alteration in reel-out speed affects the tether tension, the controller is able to track the desired force. The PI controller is also able to dampen the effect of the wind much more than the open-loop system, and its robustness toward uncertainties and disturbances especially at lower frequencies has been demonstrated. Around the trim condition the system has been linearised and the Integral I and proportional P gains are defined by using the Matlab's PID Tuner.

A feedforward winch control instead is designed to track tether force as it lies on the F_t-v_r curve between its minimum and maximum value. For a simpler implementation the curve values are stored as a polynomial formulation, and by a simple linear regression the optimal F_{tref} value can be computed based on v_r reel-out speed. The torque control input τ_{ff} is then obtained by simply multiplying the reference force by the winch radius r . The complete control scheme, developed in [21] and applied

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in the simulation framework, with the feedforward open loop and the PI closed loop control are shown in Figure 3.12.

Figure 3.12: Winch control scheme composed of a feedforward open loop and PI feedback loop. [21].

The strategy proposed above is applied for the traction phase only when the kite performs circular or figure-of-eight flight trajectories. During the reeling-in phase, the winch controller computes the required control torque to track the defined retraction force set-point by using of a PI controller with the same gains obtained for the traction phase.

A graphical representation of the winch controller tether force tracking is in Section 5.2 where the controller is tested for all the flight path considered in this thesis.

Chapter 4

Navigation and flight control system

During every flight operation phase, the kite must be guided along a predefined path in a reliable and safe way. As discussed in the literature review, different strategies can be adopted to obtain these results.

In this chapter, an outer control loop for the lateral roll controller based on the L_1 non-linear logic is developed and an inner control loop is devised with the purpose of governing the kite attitude. Finally, to fully simulate an entire pumping cycle, a finite state machine has been tasked with orchestrating the entirety of the system across its diverse flight phases.

In a real scenario the flight control system must ensure that the kite follows the predefined flight paths reliably even in a turbulent and gusty atmosphere. All these external effects can be regarded as disturbances that the control system needs to account for while trying to harness the advantageous components of the wind to drive the kite and extract the maximum amount of power from it. To further enhance safety, the controller capacity to execute evasive or adaptive maneuvers in response to exceptional conditions should be taken into account. These features are not considered in this thesis for simplicity.

In the following, a comprehensive description of the development of the control system is put forth, including a more detailed exploration of tuning and the impact of control parameters.

4.1 Lateral controller

For the lateral control of the kite, a revised version of the well-known L_1 control strategy is adopted. The L_1 non-linear logic is a simple path-following algorithm, widely used in different fields of autonomous systems, whether ground or aerial vehicles, from small unmanned drones to large commercial aircraft. As shown in [31], [17] and in a modified version in [18], this control logic emerges as a feasible and simple solution suitable for the purpose of this research.

The strategy of the controller is to select a point on the desired path that has a fixed and constant distance (L_1) ahead of the vehicle. This reference takes the name of “look-ahead” point and it is computed by projecting a radius equal to the L distance parameter on the path. The controller requires a measurement of the position and velocity of the kite, as well as the location of the desired path in order to compute the outputs, in terms of deflecting the flight control surfaces, necessary to adjust the aircraft heading and steer the vehicle toward this reference point. In this way, the controller generates a steering command that is proportional to the difference between the aircraft heading and the line passing through its center of mass and the look-ahead point.

The principal benefits inherent in this approach encompass its simplicity and minimal computational demands. Furthermore it provides superior performance, in terms of path tracking capability, relative to a basic proportional feedback law controller which calculates the steering input only based on tracking error (defined as minimum distance between actual vehicle position and closest point on the reference path).

Conversely, the potential drawback of employing this control strategy is that this type of controller might exhibit limitations when applied to high curvature or complex shape geometry paths. Furthermore, the adoption of this control approach necessitates the division of control between lateral and longitudinal components, thereby impeding the attainment of optimal control over the generated aerodynamic forces and consequentially the tether force.

4.1.1 Path definition

The flight controller needs to guide the kite to follow a predefined path both in the traction and retraction phases. The first step of the implementation of the path-following algorithm is the choice and definition of the path to be followed. In the following paragraph only the traction phase path definition is discussed, since, for the retraction phase, a slightly different approach is used and described further on in the thesis.

Usually, during the traction phase, the flight path imposed to the kite is generally

a circle or a figure-of-eight path. Under the assumption of a straight tether, during the traction phase, the kite flies on a sphere centered in the ground station, with a radius equal to the length of the tether itself. This assumption is commonly used and shared by the airborne wind energy community and allows to translate and simplify the guidance problem strategy from a three-dimensional problem to a two-dimensional plane domain on the surface of the flight sphere.

The flight paths are initially defined on a tangential plane to the flight sphere in a reference point which coincides with the center of the path itself. Given a R radius of the flight sphere computes as polar coordinate of the kite position, the center of the path can be described by the position vector $\vec{p}_{c,w}$ defined in the wind reference frame as

$$\vec{p}_{c,w} = [x_c \ y_c \ z_c]_w = R \cdot [\cos(\phi_{c,el}) \cos(\theta_c), \cos(\phi_{c,el}) \sin(\theta_c), \sin \phi_{c,el}] \quad (4.1)$$

In this way the $\vec{p}_{c,w}$ vector is aligned with the down component of the basis and it is orthogonal to the tangential plane. To complete the basis the other two components are then chosen as two orthogonal vectors, which defines the tangential plane. Vectors \vec{u} and \vec{v}

$$\vec{u} = [-\cos(\phi_{c,el}) \cos(\theta_c), \cos(\phi_{c,el}) \sin(\theta_c), \cos \phi_{c,el}] \quad (4.2)$$

$$\vec{v} = \vec{p}_{c,w} \times \vec{u} \quad (4.3)$$

complete the NED basis as the north and east direction respectively, where north direction is defined as pointing to the zenith of the wind window, and the East vector \vec{v} is obtained as the cross product between \vec{u} and the normalized component of $\vec{p}_{c,w}$.

An illustration of this reference frame for the path definition is in Figure 4.2.

From a practical point of view, a two dimensional flight path can be initially defined in the obtained tangent plane given by the predefined perpendicular vectors \vec{u} and \vec{v} .

Circle parametrization

Given the center of the path in coordinate vector $\vec{p}_{c,w}$ and the radius parameter r , a circle parametrization can be easily defined as

$$\vec{\Gamma}_{circle} = \vec{p}_{c,w} + r \cos(s)\vec{u} + r \sin(s)\vec{v} \quad (4.4)$$

where $\vec{\Gamma}_{circle}$ represents the vector of 3-dimensional coordinates of the path in the space. The variable s in the parametrization could represent a temporal dependency of the kite position which leads to the definition of a trajectory. Since the proposed guidance control strategy does not take into consideration the time variable, the

problem can be translated from trajectory to path following by considering only the geometric path definition as a set of point in the space domain and neglecting the time component.

Figure of eight parametrization

For the figure-of-eight path, different parametrizations are proposed in the literature such as the *Lissajous* curve, *Lemniscate of Bernoulli* or *Lemniscate of Booth*. The choice of one parametrization over another could lead to different advantages or disadvantages, especially in the case in which the guidance control needs to evaluate the curvature or the derivative of the path as a continue function to calculate the required path and course angle.

In case the path is then discretized in a finite set of points, the choice of the parameterization turns out to be quite arbitrary. The final choice for the figure-of-eight parametrization is the *Lemniscate of Booth*, mainly for coherence with other works and for the range and control of the shape compared to the other possibilities presented above.

Finally the *Lemniscate of Booth* figure-of-eight parametrization in the u_Γ v_Γ plane can be written as

$$u_\Gamma(s) = \frac{1}{h_\tau} \frac{b_{booth} \sin s}{1 + \left(\frac{a_{booth}}{b_{booth}}\right)^2 \cos^2 s} \quad (4.5)$$

$$v_\Gamma(s) = \frac{1}{h_\tau} \frac{a_{booth} \sin s \cos s}{1 + \left(\frac{a_{booth}}{b_{booth}}\right)^2 \cos^2 s} \quad (4.6)$$

where a_{booth} , b_{booth} and h_τ are parameters that allow to define the shape of the curve. The a_{booth} parameter influences the height of the lobes, whereas b_{booth} influences the width of the shape and h_τ represents a scale factor of the shape. Figure 4.1 shows a representation of the figure-of-eight parametrization for different values of a_{booth} and b_{booth} parameters. As explained for the circle, the concept of time independence of the s variable is applicable also for the figure-of-eight path.

Figure 4.1: Representation of the figure of eight shape for different values of parameters a_{booth} , on the left, and b_{booth} on the right.

Similar to the circle parametrization in three dimensional domain the figure-of-eight path parametrization can be expressed as

$$\vec{\Gamma}_{foe} = \vec{p}_{c,w} + u_{\Gamma}(s) \vec{u} + v_{\Gamma}(s) \vec{v} \quad (4.7)$$

where $\vec{p}_{c,w}$ is still the coordinate vector of the center and \vec{u} and \vec{v} are the two unit vectors that identify the tangent plane to the flight sphere.

Path discretization and projection

Each path can be discretized as a set of points by evaluating each curve parametrization in a finite set of values of s . The level of discretization of the path, intended as the number of target points in which the path itself is divided, will affect the smoothness and frequency of the signal that the guidance flight controller will receive as input while the kite is moving along the path.

To define the target points used as input later by the flight controller, each path is discretized in 50 points. This selection appears to be a reasonable trade-off between the number of divisions needed to achieve a moderately refined path representation, while simultaneously keeping the computational cost at a low level. A finer discretization shows no significant improvements or advantages with respect to other control parameters.

The desired path set points are initially defined on the tangent plane to the flight sphere on a fixed predefined radius value. Since the kite flight space domain is constrained by the tether length, any target point out of the flight sphere will not be reachable. To be physically accessible by the kite, each set point is then projected on the actual flight sphere, which is continuously updated and computed from the radial polar coordinate of the kite in the wind reference frame. In this way, during the traction phase the kite will fly radially further away from the ground station

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as the winch controller reel-out the tether, and at each control loop cycle the flight controller adapts the predefined path setpoint proportionally to the distance of the aircraft to the ground station so that they always lie on the flight sphere surface and the final path has a constant shape dimension during the whole reel-out phase. In Figure 4.2 both the predefined desired path and the projected one are shown for circle and figure-of-eight paths.

Figure 4.2: Circle and figure-of-eight definition in dotted blue, and projection on the flight sphere in dotted pink; representation of the NED coordinate system on which the path is initially defined.

4.1.2 Guidance strategy and turning law

After establishing the desired path, a guidance strategy is needed for effectively tracking or converging towards it, also in instances where the kite deviates from its proximity. As already presented in Section 2, soft kites usually adopt the turn rate law to steer the kite towards the desired set point. However, for fixed wing kites considered in this thesis, this law is not applicable.

The guidance strategy proposed and implemented in the flight control algorithm is a slightly modified version of the L_1 control strategy developed in [18], which is thus suitable for fixed-wing aerial vehicles or other nonholomic vehicle.

For clarity and completeness, in the following paragraphs, a description of the classical L_1 logic is presented, providing clarification on the differences with respect to the developed L_0 variant, along with the modifications employed to tailor this control strategy to the AWEs field.

General L_1 logic and turning law

The L_1 guidance logic is based on the calculation of the required centripetal acceleration needed for the vehicle to converge to the desired path.

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To implement it, it is necessary to determine a reference point by identifying a location on the desired path that is situated L_1 units ahead of the vehicle. Subsequently, the lateral acceleration needed for the vehicle to trace a curved trajectory with a radius R from its present position to the reference point can be calculated as

$$a_c = 2 \frac{V_k^2}{L} \sin(\eta) \quad (4.8)$$

where V_k is the kite current speed and η is the angle between the vehicle velocity and the vector joining the vehicle position and the reference point. An illustrative image of the concept is depicted in Figure 4.3.

Figure 4.3: Principle of L_1 guidance logic, representation of desired flight path on which the closest point to the kite and the target point are highlighted in red. Representation of the velocity vector \vec{V} and heading angle η .

By applying a controller that computes the proper input to the control surfaces of the kite, which confers the required acceleration the velocity vector \vec{V} will align towards the target point direction and will steer the vehicle to converge to the desired path. The only tunable design parameter is the L_1 distance that can be adjusted to obtain a quicker or smoother convergence to the path. In [31] the author demonstrates the tracking capability of the concept and elucidates the process of parameter tuning across various scenarios such as straight line, non-straight perturbed line, and circular path tracking. The strategy is proved to guarantee asymptotic stability straight through a Lyapunov invariant set theorem analysis. This renders the logic better suited for nonlinear systems compared to commonly employed linear controls.

Application in AWEs domain

In order to extend this concept to airborne wind energy systems, it is necessary to modify and tailor the two-dimensional formulation presented earlier. This adjustment is crucial to effectively steer the kite within a three-dimensional flight environment, as required by crosswind flight dynamics. The guidance challenge is no longer constrained to a flat plane, instead, it is now linked to the spherical surface of the kite flight envelope, to which it is physically bound.

Considering the desired flight path generation outlined in Section 4.1.1, it can be observed that at any given time, the designated target point will reside upon the identical flight sphere as that of the kite. This arrangement ensures the attainability of the target point. In this case the target vector \vec{L}_1 , which connects the actual position of the kite to the target point, and the kinematic velocity vector \vec{V}_k have thus three components in the flight space domain. To simplify and bring the logic into a two-dimensional system, the tangential plane, as shown in Section 3.3, is used as the reference relative to the reported vector forces, direction and acceleration.

To compute the heading angle η and thereby calculate the desired acceleration needed to steer the kite towards the path, both the target point vector \vec{L}_1 and the kinematic velocity vector \vec{V}_k are projected onto this tangential plane and only the components that lie on it are considered. Now, in order to efficiently control the kite direction, the projected component of the aerodynamic lifting force is employed as the centripetal force that will generate the necessary acceleration a_c . As a reasonable approximation, the lifting force vector \vec{F}_l can be assumed as aligned with the z -axis of the body reference system. To obtain \vec{F}_c , it is therefore necessary to ensure a certain roll angle of the kite with respect to the tangential plane defined by the xy_τ axis.

To better illustrate the concept, in Figure 4.4, two configurations of the kites are shown: highlighted is the current kite configuration along with its associated fixed reference system and roll angle $\phi_{\tau,act}$ with respect to the tangential plane while transparently depicted is the desired attitude configuration with a roll angle of $\phi_{\tau,des}$, and the lifting force component on the xy_τ plane that generates the appropriate centripetal force to steer the kite along the predefined path. To be taken into consideration in this formulation are also the gravitational components that act upon the kite, influencing and contributing to its dynamics. The weight force vector $\vec{F}_{g,b} = [F_{g,x} \ F_{g,y} \ F_{g,z}]_b$ can be then expressed in the body reference system. To avoid overburdening and enhance clarity in the figure, the weight components are not depicted but are nonetheless accounted for in the equilibrium equation. Furthermore, the tether force on the kite should be taken into account, but as an approximation, it is possible to consider it aligned with the z_τ , which is pointing downwards to the ground station and does not produce any component in the tangential plane. In this case, the tether force would not produce any component in the tangential plane of the flight sphere, so it does not have any contribution to the centrifugal force.

Figure 4.4: Representation of the forces and reference system on the kite, actual and desired roll angle with respect to the tangential plane.

After all these considerations, the desired roll angle $\phi_{\tau,des}$ can be computed from a simple equilibrium of forces acting on the kite onto the tangential plane

$$\vec{a}_c \cdot m = \sum \vec{F} \quad (4.9)$$

$$a_c \cdot m = F_L \sin(\phi_{\tau,des}) - (F_{g,y} \cos(\phi_{\tau,act}) + F_{g,z} \sin(\phi_{\tau,act})) \quad (4.10)$$

By appropriately collecting and solving the equilibrium equation for $\phi_{\tau,des}$, one obtains:

$$\phi_{\tau,des} = \arcsin \left(\frac{a_c m + F_{g,y} \cos(\phi_{\tau,act}) + F_{g,z} \sin(\phi_{\tau,act})}{F_{lift}} \right) \quad (4.11)$$

All the roll angles are defined not as per the standard definition with respect to the earth reference system, but in relation to the tangential plane. The conversion from these two definitions is not reported here.

Code implementation

Within this section, a concise description and clarification are provided regarding the implementation of the code associated with the guidance logic.

To enable straightforward implementation and execution speed, as outlined in Section 4.1.1, a point wise discretization has been chosen for the flight path. This necessitates the implementation of a strategy to consistently select the correct target point.

Instead of defining the L_1 distance as a control parameter, the approach implemented is essentially a discretized version of the L_0 logic, in which the distance of the target point is not defined with respect to the actual position of the kite, but instead is defined as the distance between the target point and the projection of the kite position on the desired path, that is to say the closest point.

Compared to the traditional logic, this implementation allows for a broader region of attraction toward the desired path, ensuring that the guidance system always maintains a target point on it even if the kite is situated at a greater distance than the defined parameter L_1 . This approach prevents the guidance controller from losing orientation when, for any reason, the kite deviates significantly from the predefined path.

Given the closed and crossed geometry of the flight path shapes, the selection of the right target point is not straightforward. Usually when defined as a continuous curve, the closest point and the target point can be computed by using some iterative methods such as Newton Euler within a reasonably low number of iterations. Considering instead the discrete formulation over a finite set of points, another approach is used.

In the case of study, the path set of points is stored in a matrix which contains the coordinates $[x_p; y_p; z_p]$ of each point, generated and ordered as defined by the parametrization discretization of the s variable from 0 to 2π , which is stored in a vector. As a design choice the path is composed of 50 points.

A new vector is introduced which contains the distances between the kite position and each point of the path. Each vector is defined as a cyclic array, enabling the algorithm to periodically repeat the procedure of selecting the nearest point as the kite repeatedly follows the closed path. The index within the s vector that corresponds to the nearest point along the path to the kite aligns with the index of the minimum value within the distance vector. To ensure that the closest point found is also the correct one of the sequence, it is chosen from a smaller shifted set of distance vectors whose first element is the closest point of the previous iteration. This issue arises primarily in the case of the figure-of-eight configuration, wherein, as the kite reaches the intersection segment of the path, the nearest point is not always the accurate choice for correctly tracing the path in sequential order.

Once the index and corresponding coordinates of the correct closest point are found, the target point is defined as the n -th element of the shifted vector. In this way it is consistently defined as n points ahead of the nearest point. The number of points

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ahead effectively corresponds to a discrete control parameter of the previously described variable L_0 .

The target vector can thus be computed given the coordinates of the kite and the target point, defined in the wind reference frame. By means of appropriate transformation matrices, the resultant vector, along with the kinematic velocity vector, can be projected onto the tangent plane, and the resulting components can be employed to calculate the heading angle η . To avoid unfeasible and too steep turns that could lead to dangerous manouvers, the computed heading angle η is saturated within a limited range of $\pm\frac{\pi}{4}$. Finally, by adding all the force components acting on the kite, the desired roll angle $\phi_{\tau,des}$ with respect to the tangential plane is computed.

4.2 Flight control architecture

Once the guidance block computes the desired roll angle which steers the kite towards the path, an additional controller is then needed to effectively translate the input commands into control surface deflections.

As illustrated in Section 3.4.1, the kite is equipped with ailerons, two vertical rudder and horizontal stabilizers to control its attitude in the air. As presented in [34], due to their complicated dynamics, rigid-wing aircraft are commonly controlled using a cascaded nonlinear control technique. The hierarchical structure provides separate control loops and improves performance. This strategy ensures versatility and adapts various flight situations. The method also simplifies the complex process by streamlining the application and fine-tuning of control algorithms.

Figure 4.5: Block illustration of the cascaded control architecture scheme.

In Figure 4.5, the cascaded control scheme is presented. The flight controller can be divided into lateral and longitudinal control. The lateral one is only responsible

to steer the kite and control its tangential motion on the sphere, while the longitudinal one, in conjunction with the winch controller, is responsible for the radial position and traction force. In particular the role of the longitudinal flight controller is to adjust the heading attitude of the kite, in this case by changing the angle of attack α_a to produce a required amount of lift and as a result the tether force. From the block scheme the reference roll angle ϕ_{des} given in output from the guidance block is received as input by the attitude control block. This block, through the utilization of a PID controller, computes the reference roll rate p_c based on the error between the actual roll angle and the desired one. The same methodology is employed to regulate the angle of attack. In this instance, the difference between the current angle and the desired angle is utilized as input for the PID. Consequently, this process yields a reference pitch rate denoted as q_c . A more in-depth description of the pitch controller is provided in Section 4.2.1.

Continuing along the control chain, the rate loop block takes the reference roll and pitch rate and, based on the difference from the current rates, calculates the deflection of the control surfaces of the kite using a proportional law. To account for the non-linear effect of the commands, the magnitude of the output deflection commands is divided by the square of the kite velocity. The output is then saturated within the range of ± 1 and then multiplied by the maximum deflection value. Moreover a rate limiter is applied to simulate the maximum rate limit in the actuation system. Considering the kite as stable around the yaw axis, the only control surfaces employed are the aileron δ_a deflections to reach the required roll rate, and elevator δ_e deflection for the pitch rate.

4.2.1 Longitudinal pitch controller

As described from the theory of the concept in Section 1.1.1, one of the main relevant factors that affect the power extraction from wind in crosswind flight is the tether force. The magnitude of this force is closely tied to the lift generated by the kite. To achieve a proper tension in the tether, it is necessary to appropriately control the kite angle of attack through the pitch controller. From the aerodynamic model, it is known that the aerodynamic forces generated by an airfoil can be expressed by Equation 3.6. As shown in Section 3.4.2 the lifting force defined as the vertical component, and the drag as the horizontal one, are dependent on the aerodynamic coefficients C_L and C_D , which depend on the angle of attack (α_a). Generally, the lift coefficient (C_L) increases as the angle of attack rises, until the critical stall condition is reached.

As the ultimate goal of the system is to extract the maximum amount of power from the wind, the objective in controlling the longitudinal dynamics of flight is to maintain a high lift-to-drag ratio, optimizing power generation. As can be observed from the graph in Figure 4.6 in the case of a freely flying aircraft, this optimal ratio is achieved at a specific angle of attack. Nonetheless, considering the impact of

tether drag, the peak in the Lift-to-drag curve is practically attained at the highest lift-to-drag value reachable. It is therefore important to consider not only the Lift-to-drag ratio of the kite itself, but also that of the entire system, adding the drag contribution of the tether to the C_D value of the kite. Furthermore, it is possible to assume that, for the tethered system, flying at higher lift-to-drag ratio almost corresponds to higher lift and consequentially higher angle of attack of the kite. From these considerations, it can therefore be concluded that flying at the highest lift-to-drag ratio increases power output.

Figure 4.6: Graphical representation of the lift-to-drag ratio vs angle of attack curves of a clean flying aircraft and tethered aircraft. [38]

During the traction phase, it is therefore reasonable to regard a high angle of attack value as a reference for the longitudinal flight controller. In all the simulations performed in this study, for the traction phase, an angle of attack reference value of about 4 has been chosen to always ensure that it remains consistently within the linearized region of the $C_L-\alpha_a$ curve depicted in Figure 3.7. Currently, this option is appropriate for experimental purposes; however, for a real-world application, it is crucial to make sure that the tether force does not exceed the maximum tension threshold in the case of winch controller saturation. This preventive measure is made by reducing the aerodynamic performances of the kite, typically decreasing its angle of attack.

At this point, the reference angle of attack α_{des} is used as an input reference value into the pitch flight controller. By computing, through the PI cascaded loops, the elevator deflection δ_e control output, the controller adjusts the pitch inclination of the aircraft so that the reference constant angle of attack is tracked.

While performing the circle and figure-of-eight paths, the longitudinal controller is continuously affected by external disturbances given by the winch and the tether, and by the kite dynamics. The effect of the wind plays a fundamental role in this sense. While flying up on the flight sphere in the opposite direction to the wind, the change of relative wind direction will affect the true wind speed felt by the kite, leading to an increase in the α_a . Conversely, when the kite flies downwards, the wind direction and the kite alignment converge, thus reducing the angle of attack. This change of relative wind direction generates an oscillation that the pitch controller has to deal with in order to keep the kite at a constant angle of attack. The frequency of this oscillation will thus depend on the speed at which the path is followed and will differ for the two types.

4.3 Pumping cycle

At this point, to allow the execution of a complete pumping cycle, it is necessary to define a higher-level controller that manages and orchestrates the system throughout all phases. This role is fulfilled by the state machine.

4.3.1 Finite state machine

Due to the wide range of maneuvers involved in operating the pumping kite system throughout its operational cycle, relying on a single controller or guidance scheme is impractical. In this sense the finite state machine plays the role of higher level supervisory controller able to orchestrate and manage the transition between different controllers. To optimally control the entire system, each operational phase requires different reference set point and control parameter; for example, during the traction phase, the flight controller guides the kite through a cross wind fly pattern with specific tether force reference tracked by the winch controller.

To switch among these different operational states, it is necessary to define a set of determinants (triggers) that manage each state transition.

In this case of study, a basic state machine controller is developed where only the required flight states needed to simulate a complete pumping cycle are considered. In a real application also the launch and landing procedures must be taken into account, since they require specific control actions. However, these operational phases do not cover an essential role in the case of interest.

The following subsections provide a brief description and overview of the three considered phases.

Traction phase

As mentioned before, during the traction phase the kite is steered along the predefined path by the lateral controller as explained in Section 4.1.2. The waypoints to be tracked are defined by the discretization of the circle or figure-of-eight paths. In this phase, the longitudinal flight controller tries to keep the angle of attack constant to its reference value, which allows to extract and generate the maximum amount of lift. Furthermore the winch controller continuously adjusts the tether tension by controlling the reel out speed ensuring that the force generated always lies on the optimal curve. In this phase the winch controller also guarantees that, if the kite is not producing enough lift to stay up in the air, a minimum tether force of $0.5 \cdot 10^6$ N is tracked by reeling-in. The determining factors that mark the progression into the subsequent flight phase, specifically retraction, are the kite position along the path and the length of the tether. Specifically, for the first condition, to initiate the retraction phase, the kite must be positioned within a specific section of the path defined by points s_{min} and s_{max} of the figure-of-eight or of the circle path. These sections are consistently delineated to ensure that retraction is initiated only during the kite upward flight, thereby facilitating a deceleration for a more smooth transition. The second condition, on the other hand, dictates that the retraction flag is set when the maximum length of the tether is reached. When these two conditions are simultaneously met, the transition to the retraction phase occurs.

Retraction phase guidance

At the end of the traction phase the state machine switches to the retraction flight phase. In this phase, the kite is guided by the lateral controller towards a singular target point aligned with the ground station and on one of the two sides of the traction paths. The heading angle is so computed based on the relative position of the aircraft and the predefined waypoint. To reach this point the same L_0 logic applied for the traction phase is implemented. Considering only one target point, the path way from the end of the traction phase to this final reference point is thus not precisely defined.

In this case, the pitch controller does not utilize the angle of attack, as during the traction phase; rather, it takes a predetermined descent angle to be tracked during the re-entry phase. Through the use of a simple proportional law a reference input value for the attitude block is computed based on the difference between the vertical component of the kite velocity vector \vec{V}_k and the predefined descent angle. In this state, the winch initiates the reeling in of the tether as the kite descends towards the ground station tracking a predefined tether force setpoint. The winch controller implementation is the one initially introduced in the MegAWES framework by Rapp et al. [33] [10] and proposed in a simplified version by Eijkelhof in [13]. In this case the reference torque is simply determined by a PI controller that receives as an input the error between the tether predefined force set point and the measured

tether force at the ground station. This phase is sustained until the point at which the subsequent phase is triggered by reaching the minimum tether length.

Transition phase

The transition phase is considered for controlling the critical switching from the retraction and traction phase. This step requires special attention as the transition from normal flight to crosswind conditions is highly delicate and challenging to manage.

Once the tether length reaches its minimum value, the transition phase is triggered. In this instance, the target points switch to the traction waypoints on the predefined path while the pitch controller is once again switched to control the angle of attack of the kite, tracking the highest possible α_a .

Only when the kite has reached a position close enough to the path, the traction phase is triggered and the pumping cycle begins anew. During this phase, in the lateral controller, the L_0 parameter is intentionally saturated to a value of 400 m to ensure that the calculated acceleration becomes small when the kite is far away from the reference path.

In this phase the most challenging problem is to ensure a smooth transition in the tether tension; when the kite is flying down towards the ground station the tether force is smaller by at least one order of magnitude compared to that during the traction phase. For this reason, performing what is called a flare-like maneuver just before the kite enters the traction phase allows the kite itself to slow down and tension the line.

The adopted solution is highly simplified with the aim to achieve a complete pumping cycle simulation, thus applicable only for the purpose of this study. A deeper investigation should be conducted concerning this matter, particularly with regard to the management of synchronization and communication between the winch and the flight controller.

Finite state machine scheme

All the phases described above and switching triggers among them are schematized and depicted in Figure 4.7.

Figure 4.7: Block scheme of the implemented state machine supervisory control

4.4 Tuning controlling parameters

PID Gains tuning

PID feedback loop controllers are commonly tuned using linear control theory, which can be used to create local linear models around specific operating points that provide reasonable approximation of the system behaviour within a certain range of operation. As also detailed by S. Rapp (2021) in [33], linear control theory can also be helpful to ensure that the controlled system remains stable within certain bounds and to understand the impact of control actions and disturbances on the nonlinear system.

However, due to the complexity of the control loop architecture, tuning a cascaded PID controller that involves multiple control loops becomes challenging, especially in systems that are difficult to linearize. Each loop's interaction with the others can result in unexpected behaviors, making it hard to predict the impact of changes in one loop on the overall system performance. The cascaded structure can accentuate nonlinear effects and cause instability. Moreover, tuning parameters for a linear system do not necessarily translate well to nonlinear systems. The optimal PID gains derived for linear systems might not provide satisfactory results in nonlinear contexts, leading to poor performance, instability, or even controller failure.

According to the objective of this thesis, it is not necessary to outline the details of this process, since, due to time constraints, it is more efficient to keep it simple by manually tuning the PID gains. Starting from the gain values defined and utilized by Eijkkelhof [11], the control parameters have been adjusted making use of some

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simple general rules.

In Tables 4.1, 4.2 the control gains used in the PID cascaded control loops for the traction and retraction phases are presented.

Table 4.1: Gains traction phase

Parameter	Value
Attitude Roll K_p	40
Attitude Roll K_i	5
Attitude Roll K_d	85
Attitude Pitch K_p	150
Attitude Pitch K_i	5
Rate Roll K_p	70
Rate Pitch K_i	25

Table 4.2: Gains retraction phase

Parameter	Value
Attitude Roll K_p	75
Attitude Roll K_i	5
Attitude Roll K_d	50
Attitude Pitch K_p	250
Attitude Pitch K_i	50
Rate Roll K_p	70
Rate Pitch K_i	25

A graphical representation of the cascaded control loop performances is then proposed. The tracking of the reference signal, roll angle for the lateral controller and angle of attack (α_a) for the longitudinal one, given in input to the control loop are shown. The results are referred to simulations performed at 15 m/s of wind speed and reference path parameters as defined in Section 4.5.

Figure 4.8: Roll angle and angle of attack α_a control loop tracking while following a circular path with radius 200m and elevation angle of $\phi_{el} = \pi/5$.

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Figure 4.9: Roll angle and angle of attack α_a control loop tracking while following a the figure-of-eight Down Loop path.

Figure 4.10: Roll angle and angle of attack α_a control loop tracking while following a the figure-of-eight Up Loop path.

The graphs show that the control loop can closely track the reference roll angle in each flight phase and for each path studied. In the graphs the roll angle is defined with respect to the earth reference system as output from the 6-Dofs model simulink block. The error between the actual and reference signals remains confined to a few degrees, with only a slight deviation occurring during the phase transition.

As for the longitudinal controller, it can be observed that tracking a constant signal is more challenging, and a slight oscillation of a few degrees is consistently present. This oscillating behaviour in the actual angle of attack is given by continuous changing of the true wind speed direction felt by the kite, as explained previously in Section 4.2.1. Indeed, the frequency of this oscillation varies noticeably across the various reference paths considered.

In this case, given the inherently slow system dynamics, the introduction of a derivative gain does not lead to any improvement in the reduction of this oscillation. For this reason, only the proportional and integrative part are used in the pitch attitude loop. Furthermore, also in the pitch controller, a more pronounced overshoot is evident during flight transition phases but nonetheless confined within the physical limits of the kite.

Overall, it can be concluded that satisfactory results have been achieved by manually tuning the controller parameters. However, limitations has also emerged, particularly in controlling and maintaining the kite angle of attack precisely. This does not rule out the possibility of obtaining better results through a more detailed study of the flight dynamics.

Lateral control - L_0 tuning

In regard to the tuning and influence of the sole control parameter L_0 in the guidance outer loop, shown in Section 4.5, the selection of this parameter affects significantly the accuracy in terms of cross track error of the path tracking and also affects the rate at which the kite will tend to converge toward it. Fine-tuning the parameter involves finding a balance between responsiveness and stability. The theory depicted in Section 4.1 provides insights into some general consideration about the tuning procedure. A smaller value might result in tighter control around the reference path, but it could also lead to overshooting and oscillations given by a too aggressive of the controller. A higher value of L_0 instead may result in a smoother and more stable trajectory with a reduction in the tracking precision and accuracy.

4.5 Path following results

In this section a graphical representation shows the flight controller path tracking performance to follow the desired circular or figure-of-eight path. Furthermore, a representation of the influence and tuning of the control parameter L_0 is here proposed.

The following considerations are confined to the traction phase, since only in this operational phase a precisely path following is required.

The results showcase the flight controller's capability to track different reference paths under varying control parameter settings. Moreover, also different wind conditions are tested for the circle and figure-of-eight path flown in both direction.

4.5. PATH FOLLOWING RESULTS

Circle path

In Figures 4.11 to 4.14, the tuning phase of the L_0 control parameter is presented, by using a reference circle path of 200 m radius and an elevation angle of $\pi/5$. This evaluation has been performed in a wind speed condition of $v_w = 15$ m/s. As described in Section 4.1, the control parameter L_0 basically defines the distance in terms of number of points ahead from the closest point on the path to the kite. A trade off between rapid convergence to the desired path and stable tracking must be established.

Figure 4.11: Circular path tracking with $L_0 = 14$.

Figure 4.12: Circular path tracking with $L_0 = 12$.

Figure 4.13: Circular path tracking with $L_0 = 8$.

4.5. PATH FOLLOWING RESULTS

As evident from the graph in Figure 4.11, by using a value of $L_0 = 14$ the kite never converges onto the reference trajectory but oscillates outside of it. By decreasing L_0 to 8 the kite tracks better the path with a fast convergence. It reaches a stable oscillation fairly close to the reference path with an average steady state error of about 40 m. Further reducing the value, in Figure 4.13, enhances the results in terms of convergence rate and proximity to the desired path reaching a stable tracking with a cross track error of about 20 m. An additional reduction could lead to further improvement in cross-tracking capability, but it has been observed to result in instability of the flight dynamics that leads the kite to crash. This instability can be likely attributed to the excessive aggressiveness of the guidance control in conjunction with the PID controllers.

Given the continuous curvature of the path, the kite tends to reach a configuration with an almost fixed cross track distance error to the reference path. In order to further reduce this steady-state error, a small gain in the calculation of the required centripetal force can be added. Figure 4.14 presents the results in this case, ensuring a stable convergence to the path and a small cross tracking error.

Figure 4.14: Circular path tracking with $L_0 = 12$ and offset correction with a 1.15 gain in the centripetal computed acceleration.

Once properly tuned, to prove the robustness of the control and its path tracking capability at different wind speeds, it is tested in a range from 12 m/s up to 22 m/s. The results at the minimum tested wind speed of 12 m/s are depicted in Figure 4.15, while Figure 4.16 shows the simulation results at the maximum wind speed of $v_w = 22$ m/s.

The proposed results demonstrate that the controller performs well across the entire range of considered wind conditions. The performance in terms of convergence rate and cross-tracking error remains nearly unchanged, even as the speed at which the kite follows the path varies. This, however, does not prove that a real-time adaptation of parameter settings based on the current wind speed can bring additional benefits and further improvement to the achieved results.

4.5. PATH FOLLOWING RESULTS

Figure 4.15: Circle path tracking at wind speed of 12 m/s.

Figure 4.16: Circle path tracking at wind speed of 22 m/s.

Figure-of-eight Up Loop

The same tuning process and influence of L_0 control parameter is shown for the figure-of-eight path flown in the up loop direction. The following path parameters are used: $a_{booth} = 10$, $b_{booth} = 20$, $h_\tau = 0.001$, $\phi_{el} = \pi/5$.

These values are selected in order to obtain dimensions and curvature similar to those adopted in a previous optimization study [13]. Also in this case, the results have been achieved at a wind speed of $v_w = 15$ m/s.

Figure 4.17: Figure of eight up loop path tracking with $L_0 = 5$.

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Figure 4.18: Figure of eight up loop path tracking with $L_0 = 3$.

As observable from the graphs above, the path following of the figure-of-eight requires a smaller control parameter value compared to the circle path. This is due to the more intricate and continuous variation in curvature of the path.

With $L_0 = 5$, as shown in Figure 4.17, the kite follows the reference path with a bit of overshoot coming out of the lobes, which causes the oscillation of the cross track error. This is given by the too slow response of the controller.

Decreasing the value to $L_0 = 3$, as depicted in Figure 4.18, the path tracking capability increases, reaching a fast convergence rate to the reference and a small oscillation of the cross track error with an average error of about 30 m, which is less than a wingspan.

Also in this case, after being properly tuned, the approach is tested varying the wind speed in a wind range from $v_w = 12$ m/s to $v_w = 22$ m/s in Figures 4.19 and 4.20 respectively.

The flight controller appears to perform well under all wind conditions, meaning the cross-track error stays within one wingspan and quick convergence to the reference path is ensured.

Figure 4.19: Figure-of-eight up loop path tracking at wind speed of 12 m/s.

4.5. PATH FOLLOWING RESULTS

Figure 4.20: Figure-of-eight up loop path tracking at wind speed of 22 m/s.

Figure-of-eight Down Loop

Finally, the tuning process and results are presented for the figure-of-eight flown in down loop direction, tested at a wind speed of $v_w = 15$ m/s.

The same path parameters presented for the up loop are considered.

Figure 4.21: Figure of eight up loop path tracking with $L_0 = 5$.

Figure 4.22: Figure of eight up loop path tracking with $L_0 = 4$.

In this case, the results appear to be consistent with those obtained in the opposite direction. With a L_0 value of 5, Figure 4.21, the controller guides the kite with a slight downward offset from the reference path and a gradual, slight increase in cross track error during the traction phase. Reducing the value to 4, Figure 4.22, yields improved performance in terms of cross-track error and consistency throughout the entire phase.

4.5. PATH FOLLOWING RESULTS

The same controller tuning seems to be suitable for flying the figure-eight path in both directions, demonstrating consistent robustness throughout the entire wind speed range studied (Figures 4.23, 4.24).

Figure 4.23: Figure of eight down loop path tracking at wind speed of 12 m/s.

Figure 4.24: Figure of eight down loop path tracking at wind speed of 22 m/s.

Overall performance considerations

The developed controller has demonstrated good path tracking capabilities in all of the conducted case studies, exhibiting robust performance across varying wind speeds within the investigated range.

These results are consistent with those obtained in previous studies [18] [17], demonstrating the consistency of the results achieved not only with 3 degrees of freedom models but also with the proposed 6 DoFs model.

When comparing the developed controller to more complex ones, such as the one proposed by Rapp in [33], it can be concluded that due to its simplicity, its performances in path tracking and general stability is slightly inferior but still acceptable for this case of study.

As the main limitation of the controller, the most critical point appears to be the PID tuning, which in some cases leads to unstable kite behavior and subsequent crashes. A better tuning of the PID gains might also bring to a more stable controller so that L_0 could be further decreased to obtain better path tracking.

Chapter 5

Pumping cycle simulation results

In this section, the simulation results are presented for the various types of paths studied, encompassing all distinct flight phases and thus obtaining the complete pumping cycle.

The presentation of the results is organized as follows: first, a more in-depth examination of circular paths, in which we investigated the influence of path parameters (radius of the circle in this case) at various wind speeds. Subsequently, a comparison among all three types of paths analyzed at a wind speed of 15 m/s. Finally, a comparison is presented in terms of land utilization.

It is important to emphasize that all the results from the proposed simulations are outcomes of convergent simulations. To ensure result consistency, a convergence criterion is defined. This is done to ensure that the results are minimally conditioned by initial conditions. It has been observed that, when considering only a single traction phase, the output power is significantly influenced by how the kite converges toward the reference path and, consequently, by the initial position and orientation of the kite. A simulation is thus considered convergent if a minimum of 3 pumping cycles are performed, and the difference in terms of average mechanical power produced in the last two cycles is less than a threshold of 150 kW (around 15% of the minimum average mechanical power obtained). If the latter condition is not met, and the simulation terminates due to overtime, the simulation is still considered convergent.

5.1 Circular path

Since a very comprehensive study of the figure-of-eight shaped paths has already been proposed within this simulation framework by Eijkelhof and Rapp in [13] [12] [33], the focus of this study has been shifted towards circular flight path.

The developed flight controller has enabled the testing of the effect and influence of

5.1. CIRCULAR PATH

circular path parameters followed during the traction phase, such as the radius in this case, on the average mechanical power produced and on the generated power profile within a pumping cycle. The simulations are performed by varying the radius of the path from a minimum of 180 m up to 250 m keeping a constant elevation angle between the path center and the ground of $\phi_{el} = \pi/5$. Smaller radius values have been observed to not yield significant advantages in terms of generated power and introduce instability in the flight controller. Furthermore the retraction phase is triggered when the maximum tether length of 1000 m is reached, while the transition to traction is triggered when it reaches its minimum value imposed at 700 m. The range of values for path geometry and tether length is chosen to obtain a circular path with dimensions comparable to those of the 8-shaped paths presented in previous studies and further examined in the subsequent sections of this thesis. As known from the theory in Section 1.1.1, a smaller radius centered in the middle of the wind window should provide the best performances in terms of power extraction from the wind. Moreover, the circumference size influences the difference in height; traveling along a larger radius circumference yields a higher potential energy exchange, which should result in greater amplitude of peaks in the power profile generated during the traction phase. On the other hand it is important to consider the dimensions, agility, and dynamic flight performance of the kite, which impose a physical limit on the achievable trajectories.

From Figure 5.1 to 5.4 the simulation results for the circle path are presented. In each figure in the right-hand column, the 3-dimensional graph depicts the trajectory followed by the kite during the last significant pumping cycle. The color of the trajectory highlights the mechanical power generated by the ground station at each specific point. Conversely, in the right column, the profile of generated mechanical power and the average value are highlighted.

5.1. CIRCULAR PATH

Figure 5.1: Simulation results of circular paths with 15 m/s wind speed, varying radius from 180 up to 250 m.

5.1. CIRCULAR PATH

Figure 5.2: Simulation results of circular paths with 18 m/s wind speed, varying radius from 180 up to 250 m.

5.1. CIRCULAR PATH

Figure 5.3: Simulation results of circular paths with 20 m/s wind speed, varying radius from 180 up to 250 m.

5.1. CIRCULAR PATH

Figure 5.4: Simulation results of circular paths with 22 m/s wind speed, varying radius from 180 up to 250 m.

5.1. CIRCULAR PATH

As the wind speed increases, the winch controller tends to unwind the tether more rapidly, resulting in elongated spiral trajectories.

In the case of low wind speeds (Figures 5.1, 5.2) during the traction phase, a consistent brief power consumption period can be observed. This occurs because the kite receives limited support from the wind, requiring the winch to consume power in order to maintain the minimum tether tension while ascending.

It is also evident that at the same wind speed, flying a path with a smaller radius reduces the energy consumption phase during the ascent, especially noticeable at low wind speeds. This effect is particularly visible from the simulation results conducted at a wind speed of 18 m/s, Figure 5.2. When following the circular path with a smaller radius, a consistently positive mechanical power is achieved throughout the traction phase. Conversely, when following the path with a radius of 250 m, slight negative peaks in mechanical power are noticeable.

Beyond wind speeds of 20 m/s, shown in Figures 5.3 and 5.4, the kite manages to stay supported throughout the traction phase without the winch needing to reel in the tether to ensure the kite keeps flying.

From all the shown simulations, it is also evident that at the same wind speed the amplitude of the power peaks is slightly lower when following paths with a smaller radius, as expected. Excluding the initial power peak, which is heavily influenced by the transition phase from normal flight to crosswind flight, it can be observed that the power amplitude during the traction phase increases with an increase in the reference path radius and, consequently, with an increase in altitude variation. Indeed, the greater potential energy exchanged translates into an increase in the power variation within the traction flight path.

Moreover, a decreasing trend in the maximum peak values in the generated mechanical power profile is present and clearly visible in the simulation of circular path with 180 m of radius in Figure 5.3. This effect is attributed to the fact that, given the narrower reference path and the substantial kinetic energy with which the kite concludes the retraction phase, the flight controller initially struggles to promptly converge onto the predefined path, resulting in larger-radius circles. This effect is indeed less pronounced as the reference path radius increases, because the flight controller is better able to rapidly steer the kite onto the reference path.

Furthermore, the peak power generated during the crosswind transition phase highlights how this stage is one of the most critical and challenging to manage during the pumping cycle. This phase may require specific attention, particularly to prevent exceeding the maximum tether tension or structural limits of the kite in such cases. An improved version of the pitch controller that continuously adjusts the reference angle of attack, working in synergy with the winch controller, could significantly better manage the challenges of this phase.

Interpretation and consideration results of circle path

To sum up, from this initial analysis, it can be concluded that the obtained results align with the theoretical trends hypothesized. Within the control and physical constraints of the kite, a circular path with a smaller radius appears to offer advantages, not so much in terms of average generated mechanical power value, but rather to a more compact power profile with reduced amplitude in oscillations and power peaks. However, the radius of the path does not seem to influence the generated mechanical power to a significant extent; other factors such as the flight trajectory during the retraction phase or the manner in which the transition from retraction to traction occurs appear to be more influential on the average power produced over an entire pumping cycle.

Furthermore, it is important to emphasize that the generated power values were obtained while keeping all other control parameters constant. This does not imply that conducting a more in-depth analysis or optimizing these parameters might yield different values in power output. Nevertheless, the values in the proposed results demonstrate and provide qualitative insight into the generable and extractable wind power when following these types of trajectories. As a final noteworthy result, the simplicity of control offered by this type of trajectory should be emphasized.

5.2 Comparison circular vs figure-of-eight paths

In this section, a comparison is provided between the results of circle path simulations previously illustrated and figure-of-eight path flown both in up loop and down loop direction. This proposed comparison is conducted at a wind speed of 15 m/s and a constant elevation angle of $\phi_{el} = \pi/5$ for all the paths considered. Also in this case the trigger to retraction is imposed when the tether length reaches 1000 m, However, given the different trajectory by which the kite transitions to crosswind flight in the two ways of flying the figure-of-eight, the triggers for the transition phase are different and specifically defined.

The figure-of-eight geometry parameters are the same proposed in Section 4.5. In this case of study, optimal selection of these geometric parameters has not been a primary focus. Indeed, as indicated by the study conducted by Rapp et al. [33], in low wind speed conditions, varying the path shape geometry parameters alone has a negligible effect on the average power output. This finding underscores the limited sensitivity of the average pumping cycle power output to changes in the path shape. As demonstrated in the previous Section 5.1, the same consideration can be applied in the case of circular paths. For this reason, a path with a radius of 200 m, a midpoint value within the considered range, is used as a reference in the comparison with the figure-of-eight path proposed here.

5.2.1 Circular and figure-of-eight flight paths

As a reference point for circular paths, the path with a radius of 200 m is provided and depicted in Figure 5.5.

Figure 5.5: Simulation results of circle path: on the left the 3D plot of the trajectory flown over the entire pumping cycle. The ground projection of the flight trajectory is delineated by the dashed red line. On the right the power profile generated.

As shown in Figure 5.5 the kite follows the circular path producing an average mechanical power of 1.175 MW throughout the entire pumping cycle. At this relatively low speed during the traction phase the kite needs to be pulled by the winch to compensate for the ascending phase during which the gravity force tends to slow down the kite. This results in an oscillation in the generated output power of approximately 8 MW.

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Figure 5.6: Simulation results of figure-of-eight path flown in down loop direction: on the left the 3D plot of the trajectory flown over the entire pumping cycle. The ground projection of the flight trajectory is delineated by the dashed red line. On the right the power profile generated.

Figure 5.6 shows that, flying the figure-of-eight in down loop, the kite generates a slightly lower average power output of about 1 MW. However, in this case, the oscillating behaviour in the mechanical power during the traction is much lower, with an amplitude of about 4 MW, almost a half of the one obtained with the circle path.

Figure 5.7: Simulation results of figure-of-eight path flown in down loop direction: on the left the 3D plot of the trajectory flown over the entire pumping cycle. The ground projection of the flight trajectory is delineated by the dashed red line. On the right the power profile generated.

As shown by Figure 5.7, the figure-of-eight path flown in an up loop appears to be the least favorable among the three, as it generates the lowest average mechanical power of about 847 KW and exhibits a significantly higher peak-to-mean power

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ratio compared to the other solutions. In this case the amplitude of the oscillation of mechanical power is more than 10 MW. By flying in this direction, the kite experiences greater difficulty in gaining altitude when positioned at the edges of the flight window, necessitating a more substantial winch intervention and subsequent power consumption to maintain minimal tension in the tether. This results in a lower average tether reel-out speed and, consequently, an extended duration of the traction phase and higher amplitude oscillations in the mechanical power.

Comparable values of power consumed during the reel-in phase are obtained for the circular and figure-of-eight downloop paths, approximately -15 MW, while following a slightly different retraction path in the uploop resulted in a peak negative power of 8 MW.

For a more quantitative comparative analysis of the presented results, the Crest Factor (CF) parameter of the mechanical power output signal is calculated for each flight path considering only the traction phase. The crest factor is a dimensionless that represents the ratio between the maximum peak amplitude of a signal and its root mean square (RMS) amplitude and it is a widely used parameter for comparing and quantitatively measuring the quality of power produced by a system with highly time-varying energy production. A high value indicates that the signal has power peaks significantly higher than its average power. This can cause significant waveform distortion and may require more expensive and larger electrical components to handle such peaks. Conversely, a signal with a low CF is more efficient as it reduces the need to oversize system components, thus improving the overall efficiency of the energy production system. The values calculated for each flight path are listed in Table 5.1.

Table 5.1: Traction phase mechanical power signal comparison for the three considered flight paths

	Circle	Fig-of-eight Up	Fig-of-eight Down
Abs Peak Power [MW]	5.14	7.32	4.35
Mean Power Trac [MW]	1.75	0.99	1.37
RMS [MW]	3.00	3.29	1.97
CF [-]	1.71	2.22	2.20

From this analysis, it can be concluded that the circular trajectory produced the highest average power value but exhibited a significant oscillation in power production relative to its mean value, reaching a minimum CF value of 1.71. The worst results in terms of mean mechanical power and a much more oscillating behaviour during the traction phase are produced by the figure-of-eight flown in up loop direction. A highly significant result is represented by the figure-of-eight in the down loop. When following the path in this direction, the average power produced is slightly lower than the one produced with the circular path, the amplitude of

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the oscillation is reduced, almost by half, significantly reducing the negative power peaks during the traction phase. It can be concluded that the direction in which the figure-of-eight trajectory is flown, especially in the case of heavy kites, represents a highly significant variable compared to other geometric parameters such as curvature and compactness of the path itself.

It must be underlined that this comparison is limited to this single reference wind speed; at extremely higher or lower wind velocities, the outcome may vary, favoring different trajectories under varying wind conditions. It should also be emphasized that this comparison does not take into account other potential factors at play, such as safety considerations. Flying the figure-eight pattern in a down loop may pose a higher risk compared to the other alternatives. Also in this case, it must be highlighted that constant control parameters are used, and optimal selection of those values might slightly influence the outcome of the simulations. Taking into account all the considerations and limitations described, the proposed results can thus be considered a valid comparative analysis of flight paths under average working conditions. They indeed provide a preliminary qualitative and quantitative overview, from which further studies and investigations can be developed in the future.

Winch controller performance

In the following simulations the winch controller capability to track the reference tether force tested with a 15 m/s wind speed is presented. In Figure 5.8 the system is tested following a circular path, while in Figure 5.9 flying a figure-of-eight path in down loop and up loop directions.

Figure 5.8: Tether force tracking, flying circular path of 200 m radius tested at $v_w = 15$ m/s.

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(a) Tether force tracking, flying figure of eight down loop tested at $v_w = 15$ m/s

(b) Tether force tracking, flying figure of eight up loop tested at $v_w = 15$ m/s

Figure 5.9: Winch controller performance tracking the reference tether force while following figure-of-eight flight paths.

From the presented results, it is evident that the winch controller is capable of closely tracking the tension of the optimal reference force throughout the entire traction phase for all three considered flight path. It is also evident that, thanks to the new physical parameters utilized and the control dynamics presented in [21], even when simulating the 6-DoFs system, there are no noticeable high frequency oscillations in the tether force tracking, and hence in the power output produced, as previously observed in the earlier version of the winch controller [13]. Furthermore, even with a higher tracking reference setpoint during the retraction phase, the tether force almost drops to zero due to the saturation in the winch maximum reeling in speed. In essence, the kite descends faster than the winch is capable of rewinding the tether. This makes the setpoint reference value relatively insignificant during this phase.

Comparison with the MegAWES framework

To compare the results of the developed flight controller with the one previously used in the MegAWES framework, the simulation results tested at the closest wind speed reference available of 14 m/s are presented in Figure 5.10. In this instance, the outcome is comparable exclusively with the figure-of-eight flown in up loop direction, as it is the sole option implemented in the MegAWES framework. In the presented graphs, the ranges of tether lengths throughout the entire pumping cycle are not equal for the two controllers: a larger range is considered in the MegAWES simulation. Moreover in MegAWES some controller parameters are optimised.

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Figure 5.10: Results of figure-of-eight Up Loop simulation at 14 m/s wind speed with MegAWES framework.

With the necessary precautions, some interesting considerations about the obtained performance can be made. It can be observed that the developed controller and the one in the MegAWES version behave very similarly regarding the flight trajectory. The most noticeable difference between the two is the number of complete figures of eight performed during the traction phase; despite considering a shorter rope length range, the winch controller tends to reel out more slowly. Furthermore, from the graph in Figure 5.7, it can be noted that the negative power peaks during the traction phase reach slightly lower values due to the minimum tether tension defined by the winch controller. This value could potentially be tuned and optimized for better performance. Nevertheless, the average mechanical power generated during the entire pumping cycle is very similar, around 840 kW. This result demonstrates that the simplicity of the developed flight controller, compared to the previous version adopted in MegAWES, does not appear to have significantly affected the average mechanical power output. The development of a more complex system might thus prioritize the enhancement of safety levels rather than being solely centered on maximizing power output.

5.2.2 Land usage comparison

To conclude this comparative analysis of flight path types, the flight area has been taken into consideration.

When considering the expansion of the utilization of these ground-gen airborne wind energy systems, moving from a single unit to multiple systems forming a wind farm, akin to wind turbines and wind parks, it is crucial to analyze the actual portion of the flight area and the resulting utilization of airspace for the different flight paths. In order to investigate the impact of flight paths on the portion of ground covered, several simulations are conducted for each of the paths discussed in the previous analysis, while keeping all other geometrical and control parameters constant.

In the graphical representations in Figures 5.5, 5.7, 5.6, of Section 5.2.1, the ground

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projection of the flight trajectory limits is highlighted for all three considered case studies. The area of the rectangle obtained from the limits of the projection is used as the reference surface value.

For a more accurate assessment, the only variable parameter is the maximum tether length value that triggers the retraction phase. Considering a range from 900 to 1200 m, five simulations for each path type are conducted, progressively increasing the maximum length. Taking into consideration the average mechanical power generated during the pumping cycle and the rectangular area of land defined by the outer limits of the ground projection of the flight path, the results listed in Tables 5.2, 5.3, 5.4 are obtained

Table 5.2: Simulation results for circle path (radius 200 m)

Circle path			
Sim (idx)	Mean power [W]	Area [m^2]	Density [W/m^2]
1	$1.21 \cdot 10^6$	$5.53 \cdot 10^5$	2.17
2	$1.20 \cdot 10^6$	$5.65 \cdot 10^5$	2.13
3	$1.18 \cdot 10^6$	$6.08 \cdot 10^5$	1.94
4	$1.18 \cdot 10^6$	$7.13 \cdot 10^5$	1.65
5	$1.17 \cdot 10^6$	$7.50 \cdot 10^5$	1.56

Table 5.3: Simulation results for figure-of-eight path in Down loop direction

Fig-of-8 Down			
Sim (idx)	Mean power [W]	Area [m^2]	Density [W/m^2]
1	$8.49 \cdot 10^5$	$8.85 \cdot 10^5$	0.96
2	$9.69 \cdot 10^5$	$1.10 \cdot 10^6$	0.87
3	$9.25 \cdot 10^5$	$1.18 \cdot 10^6$	0.78
4	$9.96 \cdot 10^5$	$1.23 \cdot 10^6$	0.81
5	$9.79 \cdot 10^5$	$1.36 \cdot 10^6$	0.72

Table 5.4: Simulation results for figure-of-eight path in Up loop direction

Fig-of-8 Up			
Sim (idx)	Mean power [W]	Area [m^2]	Density [W/m^2]
1	$8.43 \cdot 10^5$	$1.20 \cdot 10^6$	0.70
2	$8.47 \cdot 10^5$	$1.24 \cdot 10^6$	0.68
3	$8.74 \cdot 10^5$	$1.29 \cdot 10^6$	0.67
4	$8.85 \cdot 10^5$	$1.35 \cdot 10^6$	0.65
5	$8.63 \cdot 10^5$	$1.42 \cdot 10^6$	0.60

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The results are presented graphically in Figure 5.11: each cluster of points represents the results of simulations for each considered path, green indicating the circular path, blue depicting the figure-of-eight in a down loop, and red representing the one in an up loop.

Figure 5.11: Land usage flight path comparison: On the y axis, the average mechanical power [W] produced during an entire pumping cycle is depicted, while on the x axis, the area in m^2 of the ground covered by the kite is represented.

From the graph, it can be observed that each type of path forms a distinct grouping. The simulations obtained by flying the circular paths, on the top left side of the plot, show a higher power per unit of surface area compared to both modes of the figure-of-eight. In the case of the circular path, the average mechanical power density generated is approximately $1.89 W/m^2$.

Given the elongated nature of the figure-of-eight pattern in the horizontal direction, its ground projection covers a significantly larger area compared to the circular path. Furthermore, as previously demonstrated in Section 5.2.1, both flight directions of the figure-of-eight paths appear to generate, on average, less mechanical power. This results in the cluster of points for the figure-of-eight paths, as shown in the graph, being located in the lower-right part, corresponding to a lower mechanical power density.

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The obtained mean mechanical power density values are indeed 0.83 W/m^2 and 0.66 W/m^2 for the down loop and up loop directions, respectively.

Another aspect discernible from this graph is the trend of the obtained set of points. In a diminishing trend, the behavior of the set associated with the circular path might indicate that expanding the tether length range further does not lead to an increase in the average mechanical power generated during a pumping cycle, thus reducing its efficiency in terms of power density. On the other hand, an increasing trend is evident in the case of the figure-of-eight flown in down loop, where the extension of the maximum tether length appears to yield a higher average mechanical power, while the projected area also seems to increase almost linearly. Ultimately, the figure-of-eight path in up loop direction does not appear to exhibit a clear increase in generated mean power output with the extension of the maximum tether length.

In summary, it can be concluded that circular paths appear to demonstrate favorable performance and characteristics. In comparison to figure-of-eight paths, circular paths seem to excel both in terms of average mechanical power and power density. In these terms, flying the figure-of-eight pattern yields similar results in both directions, with a slight preference observed towards the down loop direction. Finally, it is crucial to emphasize and take into account that the very limited number of simulations in this analysis could potentially affect the accuracy and reliability of the presented results. Furthermore, a more detailed analysis and optimization of control parameters could have a significant impact on the presented results.

Chapter 6

Conclusion

In this final chapter, the conclusions and most relevant results obtained in the thesis are presented. Additionally, some considerations and limitations regarding this study are discussed, and possible directions for future research and related studies are outlined.

6.1 General conclusion

In this thesis, a basic flight controller for a fixed-wing airborne wind energy system is developed. This controller is capable of simulating the entire pumping cycle of a ground-gen system with the final aim of assessing the performance of circular flight paths and comparing them to the more extensively studied figure-of-eight paths. The simulations are being conducted within the same working environment, based on the MegAWES simulation framework where a 150 m^2 fixed-wing reference kite is used. The navigation strategy, based on a variation of the widely used L_1 logic, is proposed, tuned and tested in conjunction with a cascaded PID control loop for the attitude control of the kite. The new winch control law and its parameters are tested in the 6 DoFs system demonstrating the ability to control the tether force optimally and significantly reduce oscillations in the power curve compared to the previous version. A simple state machine has been developed to simulate traction, retraction and transition phases allowing to complete the whole pumping cycle. The developed flight controller, when properly configured, has demonstrated its simplicity and capability to successfully track all studied flight paths, exhibiting good path tracking abilities and robustness across varying wind speeds.

The analysis of circular flight paths has demonstrated their equally valid effectiveness in terms of control simplicity, average mechanical power generated and power curve. Differences and advantages have been highlighted in flying more compact circular paths to minimize potential energy variation and, consequently, reducing

the amplitude of oscillations in the generated mechanical power during the traction phase.

Finally, the comparison between circular paths and figure-of-eight paths flown in both directions has highlighted that circular paths are comparable, if not superior, with higher average power and greater compactness in terms of overflowed area. The down loop direction of the figure-of-eight, however, remains a valid alternative, as it yields a power curve with a smaller amplitude of oscillation while ensuring good average power. The up loop direction, despite being one of the most commonly used, has proven to be the less advantageous alternative for this type of airborne wind energy system.

6.2 Outlook and future research

This research has revealed several significant findings; however, it is important to highlight some considerations and limitations related to the outcomes and conclusions of this thesis.

The developed flight controller can serve as a good and straightforward alternative for testing and research compared to controllers of much greater complexity. However, further research into the robustness of the control logic under turbulence or significant variations in wind profile and direction is needed. A more significant validity of the results, especially in terms of managing power peaks, could be achieved by developing a more sophisticated pitch controller capable of better handling the lift force generated by the kite. This includes not only flying at the maximum angle of attack but also adjusting properly to the optimal tether force.

The values presented for each of the flight paths could vary significantly if optimization is performed on the control and path geometry parameters. Such optimization, considering navigation parameters and cascaded control gains, could also demonstrate greater path tracking capability. Furthermore, the proposed comparison of different flight paths was conducted at a single wind speed; hence, the same conclusions cannot be extrapolated to other wind conditions. At lower or higher wind speeds, the results regarding the optimal path may differ. Therefore, an extension of the considered wind range would increase the validity of the presented results.

Finally, it is important to emphasize that in these cases, validation through field testing of experimental data represents an essential step to substantiate the findings of this thesis.

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